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Water Quality Monitoring, Modeling and Mitigating for Rosetta Branch, Egypt

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"The most beautiful thing in engineering life is to build a hope bridge over a despair river"

Allah grants success,,,

Abstract

The River Nile has played an extremely important role in the civilization, life and history of the Egyptian Nation. The Rosetta Branch represents the main freshwater stream on the western boundary in the Nile Delta of Egypt. It is considered as one of the main sources for drinking, irrigation and industrial activities. Water quality status of the Rosetta Branch has been deteriorated in the last decades due to the aggressive human activities. Domestic and agricultural wastewaters from several drains and industrial effluents from the industrial companies at Kafr El-Zayat city are the main sources of pollution.

The main objective of this research work is investigating the water quality management of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. For that, a water quality monitoring program was planned, including each key site of Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. Monitoring system is based on field sampling and laboratory tests to secure water quality records for the study area. Thirty-two water samples were collected from the eight monitoring stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city and from the outlet of Tala Drain. These samples were collected during the period from November 2014 to August 2015. The eighteen measured parameters were: physical (water temperature, turbidity and total dissolved solid); chemical (pH, dissolved oxygen, chemical oxygen demand, biochemical oxygen demand, salinity, conductivity, sulfate, phosphate, nitrite, nitrate, chloride, iron and manganese); and biological (fecal coliform and total algae). The records confirmed the phenomenon of the death of fish in the Rosetta Branch during the summer due to the relatively low concentrations of DO.

Two water quality indices (WQIs), Canadian Council of Ministers of Environment (CCME) and National Sanitation Foundation (NSF) have been

applied to assess the present status of water quality in the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city based on the field records. Moreover, another two statistical analysis approaches, correlation analysis and factor analysis (FA) /principle component analysis (PCA), were developed to obtain the nature of correlations among the different parameters and to identify the significant sources of water pollution. Obtained results indicate that the Rosetta Branch has a good water quality status during different seasons except for summer, where a poor water quality status is dominant.

The topographical database (bathymetry and cross sections) for Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city, based on field survey, was produced using Geographic Information System (GIS).

In this work, a hydrodynamic and water quality model was developed for the Rosetta Branch based on a one-dimensional, fully dynamic and finite difference hydrodynamic and water quality code, MIKE 11. The model was calibrated using measured records from November 2014 to August 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. The results of the presented model show a good agreement with the observed hydrodynamic (water levels, water temperature and salinity) and water quality records (DO, BOD and FC). The developed model was used to test different scenarios in order to improve the water quality status of the Rosetta Branch. Based on the results, a diversion of the Tala Drain discharge to the nearest main drain is the most effective scenario. The expected decrease in the water level of the River Nile will cause deterioration in water quality of the Rosetta Branch in the next few years.

According to the results of this study, it is urgently recommended that a national water quality management plan for the Rosetta Branch should be initiated.

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List of Abbreviations

Δ	Change of reference value
AME	Absolute Mean Error
AD	Advection-Dispersion model
APHA	American Public Health Association
BOD	Biochemical Oxygen Demand
CCME	Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment
COD	Chemical oxygen demand
Cl	Chloride
C_{sc}	Parameter value due to applied scenario
C_{ref}	Parameter reference value
DHI	Danish Hydraulic Institute
DO	Dissolved Oxygen (mg/l)
DO_{sat}	Dissolved Oxygen Saturation concentration (mg/l)
EC	Electrical conductivity
ECO Lab	Ecological laboratory (water quality model)
EEAA	Egyptian Environmental Affairs Agency
FA	Factor analysis
FC	Fecal Coliform (Cell Numbers/100 mL)
GIS	Geographic Information System
HD	Hydrodynamic model
MADWQ	Monitoring and Analysis of Drainage Water Quality Project
MWRI	Egyptian Ministry of Water Resources and Irrigation
NBI	Nile Basin Initiative

NH₄	Ammonium (mg/l)
NO₂	Nitrite (mg/l)
NO₃	Nitrate (mg/l)
NRC	National Research Council
NSF	National Sanitation Foundation
PCA	Principle Component Analysis
pH	Potential of Hydrogen (unit)
PO₄	Phosphate (mg/l)
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SO₄	Sulfate
S(N)	Station (Number)
T	Temperature (°C)
TDS	Total Dissolved Solids (mg/l)
WHO	World Health Organization
WQI	Water Quality Index
WWAP	World Water Assessment Programme

Chapter (1)

INTRODUCTION

Water is considered as the most important natural resources that affect all aspects of development. Because of limited freshwater resources against the growing water demand, it is necessary to implement water quality management strategies to control water pollution which is a global problem that needs immediate attention and perfect prevention (EEAA 2007). Water quality is a term used to clear up the suitability of water to favor different uses or processes. Water quality management involves two branches; the identification and assessment of pollution sources and the determining the best management practices to meet water quality standards (Chapman 1996).

This chapter presents an introduction to the water pollution in the Nile Delta (which affects the water quality of the River Nile), the problem statement, the objectives of this study, the research methodology and the organization of this thesis.

1.1 Water Pollution in the Nile Delta

Egypt faces great scarcity challenges due to its limited share of the River Nile water as a tail country. The River Nile is divided into two branches, the Rosetta Branch to the west and the Damietta Branch to the east, forming the Nile Delta north to Cairo, as shown in Figure (1-1). The Nile Delta has the main urban areas in Egypt, it is considered as the main source of the Nile water pollution as a result of agricultural drainage, untreated industrial and municipal wastes. Water quality of the Rosetta Branch has been deteriorated

its path. The industrial companies, located at the eastern bank of Rosetta Branch [such as El-Mobidat (pesticides and chemical company), El-Malyia (fertilizer production company) and Salt and Soda Company] directly discharge their chemical effluents into the branch without any treatment in an illegal way. So, the adjacent reach of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city is subjected to two sources of pollution in a short distance. The Rosetta Branch is mainly used for drinking purpose; many drinking water plants and water intake stations for some towns are directly located after Kafr El-Zayat industrial companies (MWRI 2002). Therefore, the main objective of this research is the water quality management of Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. Ecological problems such as, the phenomenon of fish death in the Rosetta Branch significantly appears, in particular in the summer.

1.3 Study Objectives

The main objective of this thesis is to assess the water quality and ecological status in the Rosetta Branch and suggest some mitigation scenarios.

The research work can be divided into the following specific objectives:

- Organizing of a water quality monitoring program including each key site of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city.
- Implementing of a GIS water quality database for the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city.
- Assessing of the present status of water quality in the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city.
- Assessing of the ecological status in the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city.

- Developing of a hydrodynamic and water quality model for the Rosetta Branch flow at Kafr El-Zayat city.
- Addressing some feasible water quality mitigation scenarios for water quality management in the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city.

1.4 Research Methodology

The work methodology can be described as follows:

- Diagnose state of art in water quality studies related to the Rosetta Branch.
- Implementing of a water quality monitoring program for a specified reach of the branch.
- Developing of a GIS water quality database for the Rosetta Branch based on collected available hydrological, meteorological and water quality parameters.
- Utilizing of the Water Quality Index (WQI) and Statistical Analysis approaches to assess the water quality and identify major pollutant sources impacting the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city.
- Developing of a hydrodynamic and water quality model for the Rosetta Branch using MIKE 11 modeling code (calibration and verification).
- Based on the developed model, recommending of some feasible water quality management scenarios.

1.5 Thesis Structure and Organization

This thesis is divided into six chapters which may be summarized as follows:

Chapter (1) Introduction

This chapter includes an introduction to the Nile Delta and its pollution, problem statement, research objectives, research methodology and organization of the thesis.

Chapter (2) Literature Review

This chapter presents a brief introduction about the case study; Rosetta Branch, a general review of water quality management for rivers (includes water quality monitoring, modeling and assessment approaches). Moreover, previous water quality studies for Rosetta Branch will be addressed and discussed in this chapter.

Chapter (3) Study Area & Monitoring Program

The study area, the sampling procedure, the experimental work, the developing of the study area bathymetry, analysis of monitoring results and ecological analysis will be described and discussed in this chapter.

Chapter (4) Water Quality Assessment

This chapter presents the application of two assessment approaches, Water Quality Index (WQI) approach and the statistical analysis approach, for the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city.

Chapter (5) Numerical Modeling & Analysis

This chapter presents the developing and calibration of the hydrodynamic and water quality model for the selected reach of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. Moreover, based on the developed model, application of the suggested water quality management scenarios to enhance the water quality status of the study area is discussed.

Chapter (6) Conclusions & Recommendations

This chapter presents the conclusions and recommendations of this study in order to be used for further research.

Figure (1-2) summarizes the flowchart of this research work.

Figure (1-2): Methodology flowchart

Chapter (2)

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter presents a brief introduction about the case study; Rosetta Branch, a general review of water quality management for rivers (includes water quality monitoring, modeling and assessment approaches). Moreover, previous water quality studies for Rosetta Branch will be addressed and discussed in this chapter.

2.1 The Rosetta Branch Characteristics

The River Nile is the main source of freshwater in Egypt, meeting nearly all demands for drinking water besides its use for agriculture, industry, recreation and fish production. The River Nile flows from the downstream of Aswan High Dam at Lake Nasser in the south to the Delta Barrage at Cairo in the north. Northern to Cairo, it separates into two branches, the Rosetta Branch to the west and the Damietta Branch to the east, forming the Nile Delta (MWRI 2003). The Rosetta branch, as shown in Figure (2-1), represents the main freshwater stream on the western boundary of the Nile Delta. It flows from the downstream Delta Barrage to the North-West where it ends at the Edfina Barrage, 30 km upstream the sea, releases excess water to the Mediterranean Sea (El Gammal and El Shazely 2008). It is about 230 km in length with an average width of 180 m and a depth varying between 1.5 to 16 m (Elewa et al. 2009). The Rosetta branch secures demands from agricultural, industrial and domestic water supply, fisheries and recreation in the Nile Delta. The average flow rate of the branch is about 21.5 Mm³/day (Ezzat et al. 2012).

Figure (2-1): Rosetta Branch and the Nile Delta (MWRI 2005)

According to the map of Egypt distribution of the climate profile (EEAA 2010), the climatic conditions of the Nile Delta are similar to those of the northern part of Egypt, it is rather arid to semiarid, where the rate of evaporation exceeds many times the rate of precipitation. The mean minimum air temperature varies from 6.2°C in February to 23.6°C in August. The mean maximum air temperature ranges between 17.4°C in January to 34.2°C in July. The relative humidity ranges from 51% in May to 76% in December. The total annual rainfall ranged between 38.1 - 190.8 mm along the Branch from south at Shebin El-Kome city to the north at Rosetta city. The evaporation attains the highest annual mean value (6.8 mm/day) at Tanta and the lowest value (4.2 mm/day) at Rosetta (EEAA 2010).

The Rosetta branch daily receives more than 3 million m³ of agricultural drainage water, in addition to receiving untreated and partially treated industrial and domestic wastewaters (Mostafa 2014). Five main drains (EL-Rahawy, Sabal, El-Tahrir, Zawieyt El-Bahr and Tala) discharge their drainage water in the branch. Three mega industrial companies (El-Mobidat Company, El-Malyia Company and Salt and Soda Company) at Kafr El-Zayat city, are located on its banks, directly discharge their chemical effluents in the branch (Abdo 2002), as shown in Figure (2-2).

Figure (2-2): Outfalls of Main drains and industrial companies on the Rosetta Branch

Human activities, agricultural drainage, domestic wastewater and industrial effluents produce a large range of contaminants into aquatic ecosystems and cause negative effects on the environment in the Rosetta Branch (MWRI

2002). Degradation of the water quality for the Rosetta Branch is a major problem and enhancement of the water quality is one of the most important challenges in Egypt (NBI 2005). The policy of the Ministry of Water Resources and Irrigation in Egypt relies on using all the available water resources in a rational way to cover the increasing water needs (Brown et al. 2003). The major challenge of this policy is the degradation of surface and groundwater quality by domestic, agricultural and industrial pollution (MWRI 2005). A significant amount of water is discharged freely in the Mediterranean Sea every day to dilute the pollution in the Rosetta branch and prevent creep of saltwater into the Nile Delta. Preserving the aquatic life in the Rosetta branch especially fishery is another important problem (Ibrahim 2013).

2.2 Water Quality Management

Water quality management is one of the main branches of water resources management. It aims to achieve the sustainable use of water resources by protecting and improving their quality while maintaining economic and social development (Pollard and Du Toit 2008). Water quality management includes the identification and assessment of point and nonpoint source of pollution and then determining the best management methods to control pollutants and maintain their levels within the permissible values in water quality standards (Biswas and Tortajada 2009).

2.2.1 Water Quality

Water quality is an expression used to extract the suitability of water to suffer various uses or processes. Water quality represents the physical, chemical and biological characteristics of water and measures the ability of a water

body to support different uses in any region (Elshehry 2010). Researchers measure and analyze characteristics of the water then selected characteristics are compared to benchmark standards and guidelines to decide if the water is suitable for a particular use or no (Lehr et al. 2005). Water quality is affected by a wide range of natural and human influences. The most important of the natural influences are geological, hydrological and climatic since these affect the quantity and the quality of water (Bartram and Ballance 1996).

2.2.2 Water Uses Pattern

The development of civilizations has led to a shift in the pattern of water use according to: drinking, fisheries, navigation and transport, livestock watering, agricultural irrigation, industrial production and industrial cooling water (Valecha and Bhatnagar 1988). Human use of water for almost all purposes leads to the deterioration of water quality and generally limits the further potential use of the water. For example, drinking water requires the highest quality water but in relatively small quantities while irrigation water requires larger quantities and less quality (Chapman 1996). In developing countries, growth of urban region has been accompanied by increases in the pollution stress on the aquatic environment. All of these lead the rivers to become as a convenient receiver of wastes. The harmful uses for rivers disagree with the all other uses of water particularly for drinking water (WWAP 2006).

2.2.3 Water Pollution Aspects

Water pollution can be defined as the change of physical, chemical and biological characteristics of water which restrict or prevent its use in the different activities (Vigil 2003). Increasing water pollution causes not only the deterioration of water quality but also threats human health and the

balance of aquatic ecosystems, economic and social development (Khopkar 2007). There are three main sources of water pollution which potentially affects and deteriorates the water quality in the following:

2.2.3.1 Agricultural drainage water pollution

Agriculture drainage is the major point and non-point sources of pollution with a number of potential impacts on the environmental and human health. Drainage water seeping from agriculture fields are considered as non-point sources of pollution, while drains are considered as main point sources of pollution. The major impacts of agriculture drainage on water quality are: (i) changes in salinity, (ii) deterioration of quality due to fertilizers and pesticides and (iii) possible eutrophication of water bodies due to an increase in nutrients from fertilization. Major pollutants in agricultural drains include salts, nutrients (phosphorus and nitrogen), pesticide residues from irrigated fields, pathogens from domestic wastewater, toxic organic and inorganic pollutants from domestic and industrial sources (Wahaab and Badawy 2004).

2.2.3.2 Industrial wastewater pollution

The industrial pollution is an important user of natural resources and a contributor in pollution of water and soil. A large number of industries discharge their wastes into agricultural drains connected with rivers or directly discharge their chemical effluents without any treatment into the stream. These discharge lead to a significant increase in the percentage of contaminants such as suspended and dissolved solids, nutrients, oil, grease, organic matter, heavy metals and pesticides (Mashali et al. 2009).

2.2.3.3 Municipal wastewater

The domestic pollution affects water quality heavily depends on the way of disposal of this pollution. In many cases, domestic wastewater is collected

from the center of the towns or from the villages and dumping it into a nearby irrigation canal. Therefore; domestic waste disposal significantly contributes towards water quality degradation. Generally, the bulk of treated and untreated domestic wastewater is discharged into agricultural drains. The constituents of domestic and municipal wastewater are: pathogens, parasites, nutrients and suspended solids (Wahaab 1995).

2.3 Water Quality Monitoring for Rivers

A water quality management requires information including the present status of water quality, the influence of human activities on water quality and the standard for the present and planned uses (Khan et al. 2008). Water quality monitoring can be defined as the effort of securing quantitative information on the physical, chemical and biological characteristics for a water body over time and space by typical samples taken from the water resource being monitored (Strobl et al. 2006). The basic elements of a monitoring program include: defining what will be monitored, what parameters will be measured, when and how frequently it will be measured, and where it will be measured (Khopkar 2007). Long term monitoring programs of water quality are an adequate approach to a better knowledge of river hydrochemistry and pollution (Oprean et al. 2008).

2.3.1 Water Quality Parameters

The water quality parameters can be divided into three groups which are physical, chemical and biological, as the following examples:

2.3.1.1 Physical parameters

- Water Temperature

Temperature is an important factor since it effects directly on the survival and distribution of the aquatic organisms in the aquatic environment. Water temperature is critical control parameter which influences the other physical, chemical and biological parameters (Chapman 1996).

- Total Dissolved Solid (TDS)

The total dissolved solid consist of inorganic salts and dissolved materials. It indicates the presence of dissolved materials that cannot be removed by conventional filtration (Boyd 2000).

- Turbidity

Turbidity is a measure of the clarity or cloudiness of water. It is measured by the amount of light scattered by the particles in the water as nephelometric turbidity units (NTU). Turbidity indicates the amount of fine particles suspended in water (Boyd 2000).

2.3.1.2 Chemical parameters

- pH

The pH value represents the hydrogen ion activity and influences many biological and chemical processes within a water body. The pH scale is from 0 to 14, with pH 7 representing a neutral condition in water. At greater hydrogen ion H^+ concentrations, pH will be below 7.0; the solution is acidic. At greater hydroxide ion OH^- concentrations, pH will be above 7.0; the solution is basic or alkaline. The highly acidic or highly alkaline waters are undesirable (Chapman 1996).

- Dissolved oxygen (DO)

Dissolved oxygen is a measure of the amount of oxygen freely available in water. There are many factors effect on the amount of oxygen in natural water such as temperature, salinity, amount of mixing between air and water, pH, photosynthetic activity of phytoplankton, living organisms and decomposition of organic matter (Edejer et al. 2003).

- Salinity

Salinity is a measure of the content of salts in soil or water. Salts are highly soluble in surface and groundwater and can be transported with water movement. The main cause of salinity is the application of large discharges of irrigation water and the seawater intrusion (Chapman 1996).

- Electrical conductivity (EC)

Conductivity is a measure of the ability of aqueous solution to carry an electric current. The conductivity of a water sample gives an indication of the amount of dissolved ions in the water. The more ions dissolved in a solution, the greater the electrical conductivity (Bartram and Ballance 1996).

- Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD)

Biochemical oxygen demand is a measure of the total amount of oxygen removed from water biologically or chemically. BOD is the amount of dissolved oxygen which needed by aerobic biological organisms in water to break down organic material by microorganisms. Also, it indicates the total concentration of DO that is required during the oxidation of some inorganic matter. BOD rapidly depletes DO content of polluted water with sewage and domestic, so it is important to estimate the amount of these pollutants in the water body (Kathuria 2006).

- Chemical oxygen demand (COD)

Chemical oxygen demand is the total amount of oxygen required to oxidize all the organic matter completely in water to CO_2 and H_2O . It represents the reduction of DO caused by chemical reactions. The larger the COD value, the more oxygen the wastewater discharge demands from the receiving water body. COD is used as a measure of the pollutants which present in the effluents resulting from sewage and industrial waste (Vigil 2003).

- Ammonia (NH_3)

Ammonia is often the primary form of nitrogen dissolved in an aquatic system and is the major form of nitrogen used for algal growth. It is a dissolved inorganic form of nitrogen. Ammonia is released from the action of heterotrophic bacteria, which is defined as the bacteria that oxidize organic matter for energy. Although the ammonia molecule is a nutrient required for life, excess ammonia may accumulate in the organism and cause alteration of metabolism or increases in body pH (Chapman 1996).

- Nitrite (NO_2)

Nitrite is an intermediate in the oxidation of ammonia to nitrate. Nitrites can be reduced to nitrogen gas, which returns to the atmosphere, by a process called denitrification which is carried out by a special type of bacteria under anaerobic conditions. Nitrite exists usually in very low concentrations in freshwaters because the nitrogen will tend to exist in the more reduced (NH_3) or more oxidized (NO_3) forms (Elshemy 2010).

- Nitrate (NO_3)

Nitrate is a measure of the oxidized form of nitrogen. Ammonia can be converted to nitrite then to nitrate by a process called nitrification, under

aerobic conditions. Nitrate is an indicator for the leaching of nutrients from agriculture and treatment plants (Sigeer and Microbiology 2005).

- Phosphate (PO_4)

Phosphorous is usually in water bodies in the form of phosphate ion (PO_4). It is an essential nutrient for living organisms. Phosphate is the primary form of phosphorus for algal uptake. Excessive phosphorus causes algae blooms, which are harmful to most aquatic organisms. They may cause a decrease in the DO levels of the water. This can result in a fish kill and the death of many organisms (Chapman 1996).

- Sulfate (SO_4)

Sulfate concentrations vary nearly in natural water, according to the nature of the land through which they flow. Industrial discharges and atmospheric precipitation can increase significant amounts of sulfate to surface water. High concentrations of SO_4 may make water unpleasant to drink (Boyd 2000).

- Chloride (Cl)

Chloride varies widely in natural water and reaches a maximum in sea water. Higher concentration of chloride can occur near sewage, agriculture drains and due to slate water intrusion in coastal areas. High concentration of chloride can make water unfit for use as drinking water. Chloride is one of the usual toxic ions in irrigation water with sodium and boron (Vigil 2003).

- Trace elements (heavy metals)

Trace elements are micronutrients that located beside some of the anions and cations in natural water but are at much smaller concentrations. Heavy metals, such as Mn, Fe, Zn and Cu, when present in low concentrations are important for the physical functions of living tissue and regulate many biochemical processes. Elevated concentrations of trace metals can have

negative consequences for both wildlife and humans. These metals enter rivers from a variety of sources: the rocks and soils directly exposed to surface water, decomposed vegetation and animal matter and the discharge of treated and untreated liquid wastes (Sigeo and Microbiology 2005).

2.3.1.3 Biological parameters

- Fecal coliform (FC)

Fecal coliform is a form of bacteria found in human and animal waste. Fecal coliform are bacteria whose presence indicates that the water may have been contaminated with human or animal fecal material. If fecal coliform counts are high in a site, it is very likely that pathogenic organisms are also present, and this site is not recommended for swimming and other contact recreation. Fecal coliform bacteria are living organisms unlike the other conventional water quality parameters. The presence of these indicative organisms is evidence that the water has been polluted with feces of humans or other warm-blooded animals. Untreated sewage, poorly maintained septic systems and farm animals which access to streams can cause high levels of fecal coliform bacteria to appear in a water body (Bartram and Ballance 1996).

- Total algae

Algae are aquatic plants that contain chlorophyll and grow by photosynthesis. Most algae have chlorophyll as the primary pigment for carbon fixation. Algae uptake nutrients including phosphate, ammonium, nitrate, silica and carbon dioxide from the water or benthic sediments and release oxygen to the water. Algae are often grouped based algal adaptability to environmental conditions, such as temperature, light and nutrient conditions. Algae play a key role in the eutrophication process and are essential for water quality modeling. Algae affect the nitrogen cycle, the phosphorus cycle, the DO

balance and the food chain, primarily through nutrient uptake and algae death. As algae grow and die, they form part of the nutrient cycles (Chapman 1996).

2.3.2 Ecological Analysis

There are particular chemical and biological parameters which have played an extremely important role in the ecological life. The increase or decrease in the concentration of these parameters negatively affect in survival of living organisms.

Dissolved oxygen (DO), is the most important water quality parameter which controls the life and health of aquatic organisms in water. It varies in relation to temperature, biological activity (i.e. photosynthesis and respiration) and phytoplankton blooming. It is controlled to susceptibility of fish to toxicity by chemicals which increase at low oxygen concentration (Abou El-Gheit et al. 2012). One way to sustain healthy fish is to maintain sufficient levels of dissolved oxygen in rivers by controlling of algae blooms. This way requires limits on the nutrient loadings to the river that can cause algae blooms and subsequent dissolved oxygen deficits.

When nutrients are discharged into the river, a rapid growth of algae in the surface occurs. When the algae die, they drop to the river bottom and become a source of carbon for decomposing bacteria. As more and more algae die, all the available dissolved oxygen in the bottom will be used by the aerobic bacteria in the decomposition process. When this occurs, anaerobic bacteria activity will start biological respiration in the bottom, including that one related to decomposition processes, reduces DO concentrations (Weiner and Matthews 2003). In severe cases of reduced oxygen concentrations, anaerobic conditions can occur (0 mg/L of oxygen), particularly close to the sediment-

water interface as a result of decaying material. Concentrations below 5 mg/l may adversely affect the functioning and survival of biological communities and below 2 mg/l may lead to the death of most fish (Chapman 1996).

The negative effects of excessive nutrients and the phenomenon of the death of fish in river are shown in Figure (2-3).

Figure (2-3): The negative impacts of excessive nutrients in river (NRC 2001).

2.3.3 Water Quality Measurement Equipment

The water quality may be described in terms of the concentration and state (dissolved or particulate) of some organic and inorganic material present in the water in addition to physical characteristics of the water. It is determined by in situ measurements and by examination of water samples on site or in

the laboratory (Chapman 1996). The main elements of monitoring program are on-site measurements, the collection and analysis of water samples, the study and evaluation of the analytical results. The results of analyses performed on a single water sample are only valid for the selected location and time at which that sample was taken (Bartram and Ballance 1996). Analyses of the important physical, chemical and biological parameters can be carried out in the field using equipment made specifically for field use. This equipment is mostly fitted with a range of sensors that are used in direct measurement (MADWQ 2000). A significant advantage of field equipment is that tests are carried out on fresh samples whose characteristics have not been contaminated or otherwise changed as a result of storage in a container. This is of special importance for samples that are subjected to microbiological analysis but cannot be transported to a laboratory within the time limits or under the conditions (Bartram and Ballance 1996). Some parameters must be measured in the field, either in situ or very soon after the sample has been collected. For example, field equipment is necessary for temperature, transparency and pH. While dissolved oxygen may be determined in the field or the sample may be treated in the field and the remainder of the analysis completed in a laboratory (APHA 2005).

2.3.4 Water Quality Analysis Using GIS

Geographical Information System (GIS) is a frontier branch of science which integrates space, survey, mapping science, geography, information, computer, environmental and management science (Maidment 2002). Water quality is affected by a variety of natural and human factors including hydrology, climate, geology, pesticide and fertilizer use, chemical effluents and urbanization. As the data are often measured in different units at different

temporal and spatial scales and the data sources are very various, the spatial analysis of these and other factors is a time-consuming and complicated task when performed manually (Whiteaker et al. 2006). The computer-based geographic information system is a tool that allows analysis of all various types of data. Geographically, it encodes analyses and displays multiple layers of referenced information. GIS is capable of combining large volumes of data from a variety of sources. It is a useful tool for many aspects of water quality investigations. It can be used to identify and determine the spatial extent and causes of water quality problems (Demirel et al. 2007).

2.4 Water Quality Assessment for Rivers

The output data from water samples can be in the form of complicated matrix with large parameters. In most cases it is difficult to get significant information from a complex water quality data set. Water quality assessment is the process of estimation the nature of the water body by simplifying these complex data. This process comes after the water quality monitoring which is the collection of the appropriate information about water quality characteristics (Chapman 1996). The quality of water depends on many numbers of physical, chemical and biological parameters. Therefore, it is necessary to use water quality assessment as an estimated approach to indicate the overall water quality condition. There are four main approaches which are used to assess the water quality: water quality index, trophic status index, statistical analysis, biological analysis approaches (Elshehry 2010).

In this research work and due to the nature of rivers, water quality index and statistical analysis approaches will be used to assess the water quality state of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city.

2.4.1 Water Quality Index Approach

Water Quality Index (WQI) is a scale used to assess an overall quality of water based on the records of physical, chemical and biological water quality parameters using specific methods (Simoes et al. 2008). WQI is a mathematical tool used to integrate complex data to generate a single number that describes the status of water quality to the public, decision and policy makers (House 1989). It may also be used for comparing the quality of different water sources and monitoring the temporal changes in water quality. It has been frequently used for rivers, lakes and groundwater all over the world (Tyagi et al. 2013).

A great deal of consideration has been given to the development of WQI methods since (Horton 1965) proposed the first WQI (Abbasi 2012). Horton Quality Index has the advantage that it is relatively easy to apply due to its simple structure. Since then, the formulation and use of indices have been strongly supported by institutions responsible for water supply and water pollution control (Liou et al. 2004). There are different water quality indices computation methods currently. Examples for various water quality indices which have been developed for general and specific uses are: National Sanitation Foundation Water Quality Index (NSFWQI), Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment Water Quality Index (CCMEWQI), Florida Stream Water Quality Index (FWQI), British Columbia Water Quality Index (BCWQI), and Oregon Water Quality Index (OWQI) (Abbasi 2012). The basic differences among these indices are the way their sub-indices (quality variables) were developed. These indices are often based on the varying number and types of water quality parameters (Neswiswi 2015).

The indices chosen for this research work are the Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment Water Quality Index (CCMEWQI) and the National Sanitation Foundation Water Quality Index (NSFWQI) which are two of the best known indices in water quality and have been frequently used.

2.4.1.1 National Sanitation Foundation Water Quality Index (NSFWQI)

NSFWQI was developed by the National Sanitation Foundation (NSF) in 1970 based on the selection of parameters, developing a common scale and assigning weights (Brown et al. 1970). Nine water quality parameters are used for this index: dissolved oxygen, fecal coliform, pH, biochemical oxygen demand, temperature change, total phosphate, nitrate, turbidity and total solids (Kumar and Alappat 2009). The water quality parameters are transferred to a weighting curve chart, which ranges from 0 to 100, where a numerical value of Q_i is obtained. The weight factor for each parameter is based on its test's importance in water quality. The index is computed as the weighted sum of sub-indices (Bharti and Katyal 2011).

For this research work, parameters weight factors, sub-index rating graphs and rankings are presented in Appendix (A).

NSFWQI can be calculated as follows (Abbasi 2012):

$$\text{NSFWQI} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i \times Q_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i} \quad (2-1)$$

Where: W_i : weight factor of the i^{th} parameter (Appendix A).

Q_i : sub-index quality value i^{th} parameter, can be obtained from the appropriate sub-index rating graph (Appendix A).

Many countries all over the world use NSFWQI in their annual reports on the water quality of rivers and streams under their jurisdiction (Smith 1990). NSFWQI was used to represent the water quality status of Aydughmush River, Iran (Shokuhi et al. 2012). In India, NSFWQI was used to represent

the water quality of Chambal River (Kumar et al. 2014). Effendi and Wardiatno used the NSFQI and Pollution Index to assess the water quality based on water sampling records in the Ciambulawung River, Indonesia (Effendi and Wardiatno 2015).

2.4.1.2 Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment Water Quality Index (CCMEWQI)

CCMEWQI was developed by the administration of Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment (CCME) in 1997 to simplify complex water quality data (CCME 2001). The CCMEWQI is a mathematical tool that tests various water quality parameters against specified water quality benchmarks (standards) which are determined by the user. The standards for each parameter are numeric values that define physical, chemical and biological characteristics of the water that cannot be exceeded without causing harmful effects (Poonam et al. 2013). The CCMEWQI combines three measures of variance (scope, frequency and magnitude) to produce a single unit less number that represents overall water quality for each specific site and water use relative to the objectives chosen (Khan et al. 2005). The detailed formulation of the WQI is described in the Canadian Water Quality Index 1.0 – Technical Report (CCME 2001). CCMEWQI can be calculated according to the following equation (CCME 2001):

$$\text{CCMEWQI} = 100 - \sqrt{\frac{F_1^2 + F_2^2 + F_3^2}{1.732}} \quad (2-2)$$

Where: F_1 represents scope: The percentage of variables above the standards.

F_2 represents frequency: The frequency by which the objectives are not met.

F_3 represents amplitude: The range to which the failed tests are above the standards.

The constant, 1.732, is a scaling factor (square root of three) to ensure the index varies between 0 and 100.

The factors equations, method of calculations and categories are presented in Appendix (A). While the used water quality standards for this study are presented in Chapter No. 4.

The CCMEWQI has been used in several water quality data nationally (in Canada) and internationally (CCME 2004). CCMEWQI was modified to meet requirements in classification of surface waters according to European and Asian legislation (Alves et al. 2014). In Egypt, CCMEWQI was modified based on the Egyptian standards for various uses such as drinking, irrigation, livestock, aquatic life and recreation in the River Nile in 2008 (Khan et al. 2008).

Sharma and Kansal evaluated the ability of the CCMEWQI to describe the level of pollution in the Yamuna River, India for a period of 10 years (2000–2009) (Sharma and Kansal 2011). The CCMEWQI was applied to assess water quality of Danube River, Serbia in 2010 (Jakovljević 2012). In India, Sarkar and Mishra developed the CCMEWQI to estimate the overall water quality in the Haora River (Sarkar and Mishra 2014). The modified CCMEWQI was applied to evaluate the water quality by integrating observed water quality parameters in the Karun River, Iran in 2016 (Rnjbar Jafarabadi et al. 2016).

In 2009, Mojahedi and Attari used NSFQI and CCMEWQI to evaluate water quality for the case of the Karun River system in Iran (Mojahedi and Attari 2009). Elshemy developed these water quality indices to estimate the overall water quality status of Lake Nubia in the River Nile in 2010 (Elshemy

2010). Also, NSFQI and CCMEWQI were applied to assess the status of water quality based on analysis of water sample collected along the Surma River, Bangladesh (Ray et al. 2015).

2.4.2 Statistical Analysis Approaches

Monitoring data are usually characterized by high variability because of the variety of natural and anthropogenic influences. The statistical analysis are the best approaches to avoid delusion of these data (Simeonov et al. 2002). Statistical analysis approaches are application of environmental techniques which help in the interpretation of complex data to better understand the water quality and ecological status of the studied systems. They also allow for identification of possible factors that influence water system (Shrestha and Kazama 2007). Statistical assessment of complex records is useful in the identification of pollution sources and the understanding of spatial and temporal variations for river water quality management (Reghunath et al. 2002).

The statistical analysis approaches chosen for this research work are correlation analysis (r), factor analysis (FA) and principle component analysis (PCA).

2.4.2.1 Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis is a useful tool to establish the relationships between physical, chemical and biological characteristics of water samples (Parizi and Samani 2013). It can help in selecting a few parameters which could be frequently measured to assess the status of water quality. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) value is determined using correlation matrix to identify the highly correlated and interrelated water quality parameters (Khatoun et al. 2013). The physical, chemical and biological parameters for

all the study stations were analyzed by calculating Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) value. For correlation coefficients, correlation matrix is applied by calculating the coefficients of different pairs of parameters and correlation for significance which is further tested by applying p value. Generally, the result of the correlation analysis is considered in the subsequent interpretation. A high correlation coefficient (near 1 or 1) means a good positive relationship between two variables and its value around zero means no relationship between them at a significant level of $p < 0.05$. The parameters show ($r > 0.7$) are considered strongly correlated whereas (r between 0.5 and 0.7) shows moderate correlation (Kumar et al. 2006).

2.4.2.2 Factor Analysis and Principle Component Analysis

Factor analysis (FA) and Principal component Analysis (PCA) are a powerful technique for pattern recognition that attempts to explain the variance of a large set of inter-correlated variables and transforming into a smaller set of independent (uncorrelated) variables (Singovszka and Balintova 2012).

Factor analysis (FA) is one of most important statistical methods to yield the general relationship between measured water quality parameters by showing multivariate patterns that may be help to classify the original data (Liu et al. 2003). The aim of the factor analysis of the monitoring data is to explain the observed relationship in simple terms expressed as a new set of variables called factors (Thivya et al. 2014). FA is very useful in the analysis of data corresponding to large number of variables. It produces easily interpretable results (Boyacioglu 2006).

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a statistical method which is used to determine components that are in linear combinations of the original variables (Jolliffe 2002). It is a powerful technique that attempts to explain

the variance of a large dataset of inter-correlated variables with a smaller set of independent variables or principal components (Simeonov et al. 2003). The main concept of PCA is to reduce the dimensionality of a data set consisting of a large number of interrelated variables, while retaining as much as possible of the variation present in the data set. PCA is applied to extract the principal factors corresponding to the different sources of variation in the data (Costello and Osborne 2011).

Generally, PCA and FA are designed to reduce the number of variables to a small number of indices while attempting to preserve the relationships present in the original data (Garizi et al. 2011). Correlation of principal components and original variables is given by loadings. Loading reflects the relative importance of a variable the component and does not reflect the importance of the component itself (Kebede 2012). Factor loadings can be classified as “strong”, “moderate” and “weak” corresponding to absolute loading values of > 0.75 , $0.75 - 0.50$, and $0.50 - 0.30$, respectively (Liu et al. 2003).

Several studies used statistical analysis approaches, particularly principal component coefficient. In 1999, Mazlum et al. determine factors that caused variations in water quality at the monitoring stations in the Sakarya river, Turkey using principal component analysis (PCA). The results confirmed that PCA is more reliable than factor analysis and it a pure mathematical technique without any assumption (Mazlum et al. 1999). Iyer et al. constructed a statistical model which based on the PCA for coastal water quality data from the Cochin coast in south west India, which explain the relationships between the various physical and chemical variables that have been monitored in 2003 (Iyer et al. 2003). Han et al. used the factor analysis to study the water quality of the Nakdong catchment, South Korea where it

indicated the strong effect of BOD, COD and TP on the river (Han et al. 2009). In 2013, Wang et al. applied the principal component analysis and factor analysis to evaluate temporal and spatial variations in water quality and identify latent sources of water pollution in the Songhua River, China. The results indicated that the parameters responsible for water quality variation in the region were mainly related to organic pollution and nutrients (Wang et al. 2013).

2.5 River Water Quality Modeling

Water quality modeling is the development of abstractions of the phenomena of real aquatic systems. The main objective of river water quality modeling is to describe and predict the observed effects of a change in the river system. The usual application of a water quality model is for forecasting changes in water quality parameters resulting from changes in the quality, discharge and location of the point or non-point sources (Chapra 2008). Water quality models can be used to predict the characteristics of water quality conditions in aquatic systems in order to ensure the water quality objectives will be maintained under a wide variety of conditions. They can be useful tools to simulate and predict the levels, distributions, and risks of chemical pollutants in a water body (Palmer 2001). These models provide the ability to develop a water quality management programs. They are continually being developed and improved to optimize the demands of environmental regulations and protection. The modeling results from water quality models under different pollution scenarios are very important components of environmental impact assessment and can provide a basis and technique support for environmental management agencies to make right decisions (Thomann and Mueller 1987).

2.5.1 Spatial characteristics

Water quality models are divided into four categories ranging from the simplest zero dimensional to very complex three dimensional models. The dimensions simulated by a particular model provide information on both the complexity of a model and its suitability to specific applications (Palmer 2001). For river, the water and contaminants are assumed to travel spatially in the downstream direction of the stream in one dimensional (1D) models. The advection and dispersion processes are also assumed to occur in just one direction along length of the stream. The stream is assumed to be completely (and instantaneously) mixed across its width and depth (Schnoor 1996).

2.5.2 Modeling approaches

Water quality modeling can be classified into three basic approaches: physical (experimental) modeling, empirical (black box) modeling and mathematical (mechanistic) modeling. In contrast to the empirical and mathematical models reflect how changes in system performance are related to changes in inputs (Reckhow and Chapra 1983). Mathematical modeling forms the foundation for computer modeling, while both physical and empirical modeling approaches provide valuable information to the mathematical modeling process (Gandolfi et al. 1996).

2.5.3 Mathematical modeling

A mathematical model is representation in mathematical terms of the behavior of real system which is consists of a set of mathematical equations that translates a conceptual understanding of any process into quantitative terms (Dahl and Wilson 2001). Mathematical water quality models are the models that by means of mathematical tools express the mechanisms of the

process that cause changes on water quality. These models increase the understanding of the water quality in a particular stream and provide information on cause and effect relationships as well as the ability of prediction (Reckhow and Chapra 1983). The development of mathematical water quality models should proceed according to certain general rules. The overall approach of mathematical modeling is illustrated in Figure (2-4).

Figure (2-4): Modeling methodology (Khandan 2001)

2.5.4 Governing Equation

The unsteady flow in a river can be described by two partial differential equations: the continuity equation which takes into account the continuity of the mass flow and the momentum equation which represents the dynamics effects of the flow. The governing equations of the one dimensional dynamic model for open-channel flows are the de Saint Venant equations (Wu et al. 2004):

$$\frac{\partial A_x}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x} = q \quad (2-3)$$

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \left(\frac{\alpha Q^2}{A} \right)}{\partial x} + gA \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} - gA(S_o - S_f) = 0 \quad (2-4)$$

Where: Q is the discharge (m³/s); A is the flow area (wetted cross-sectional area) (m²); q is the lateral flow (m²/s); t is the time, x is the distance downstream; g is the acceleration due to gravity (m/s²); R is the hydraulic radius (m); α is the momentum coefficient; S_o is the bed slope and S_f is the friction slope.

The transport of substances in a river can be described by the 1-D advection-dispersion equation (Vieira and Wu 2002):

$$\frac{\delta AC}{\delta t} + \frac{\delta QC}{\delta x} - \frac{\delta}{\delta x} \left(AD \frac{\delta C}{\delta x} \right) = -AKC + C_2 q \quad (2-5)$$

Where: C is the concentration; D is the dispersion coefficient; A is the cross-sectional area; K is the linear decay coefficient; C₂ is the source/sink concentration; q is the lateral inflow; x is the space coordinate and t is the time coordinate.

2.5.5 Finite Difference Method

Finite-difference method (FDM) is a numerical method for solving differential equations that express the mass conservation and momentum

conservation which consider the basis of water quality models. The finite difference method is built up from a series of nodes, and it is used for interpolating between the grid points (Socolofsky and Jirka 2002), as shown in Figure (2-5). In the finite difference, the differential equations are discretized over the numerical grid, and derivatives become difference equations which are functions of the surrounding cells. Due to finite difference methods are easier to implement and understand, so these methods are more widely used (Scott and Jirka 2002).

Figure (2-5): Finite-difference computational grid

2.5.6 Review of available hydrodynamic and water quality models for rivers

There are a large number of available models in the literature, which can be used for water quality and waste load allocation predictions. Some well-known and widely used mathematical models for water quality in rivers and catchments are listed in Table 2-1, with the indication of the institutions in which they have been developed.

Table (2-1): Principal water quality models for rivers

Model Name	Institution / Country	Year	Purpose	Ref.
QUAL2E	EPA / USA	1970	Pollution transport	(Brown and Barnwell 1987)
HSPF	EPA / USA	1970	Water flow and pollution transport	(Donigan et al. 1984)
CE-QUAL	USCE / USA	1982	Water flow and water quality	(Wells and Cole 2000)
WASP	USACE / USA	1983	Water quality and sediment transport	(Ambrose et al. 1993)
DELWAQ	DH/ Netherlands	1985	Pollution transport	(Postma 1990)
MIKE 11	DHI / Denmark	1987	Water quality and sediment transport	(Hanley et al. 1998)
DUFLOW	ASCE / Netherlands	1989	Water flow and water quality	(Parrish III and Burt 1993)
AQUASIM	EAWAG / Switzerland	1994	Substance transport and transformation	(Reichert 1998)

Most of the water quality models, with exception to very simple approaches, are computer based. A variety of modeling codes are available for water quality simulation. This software use different calculation approaches and contain varying features and limitations. While making choice between the water quality models, it is important to be very clear about the objectives of the study and any limitations within which it will be undertaken (Cox 2003).

2.5.7 MIKE 11 Model

MIKE 11 model was selected for the simulation of water quality of the Rosetta Branch in the present study. MIKE 11 was developed by the Danish Hydraulic Institute (DHI), Denmark. It is a fully dynamic and one-dimensional modeling tool for simulating steady and unsteady flows, water levels, sediment transport and water quality in river systems. It consists of a set of modules that allow users to simulate the type of hydrologic and water quality process (DHI 2012).

The Hydrodynamic module (HD), advection-dispersion module (AD) and ecological laboratory module (ECO Lab) were used for the purpose of simulation in this research.

The hydrodynamic module (HD) is the core of the system in MIKE 11 model. It uses an implicit, finite difference scheme for the computation of the flow in the rivers. The module can describe sub-critical as well as super-critical flow conditions through a numerical scheme that adapts in time and space according to the local flow conditions.

MIKE 11 HD module solves the equations of conservation of continuity and momentum (the Saint Venant equations). The solutions to the equations are based on the following assumptions (DHI 2012):

- The fluid is incompressible and homogeneous.

- The flow is mainly one-dimensional, i.e. there is uniform velocity and water level is horizontal across each cross-section.
- The bed slope is a small, thus the cosine of the angle it makes with the horizontal may be taken as 1.
- The wave lengths are large compared to the water depth, assuming that the flow everywhere can be assumed to flow parallel to the bottom (i.e. vertical accelerations can be ignored, and a hydrostatic pressure variation in the vertical direction can be assumed).

MIKE 11 advection-dispersion module (AD) can simulate first-order decays of determinants. The transport of solutes is simulated by an AD module which solves the same 1D equation of conservation of mass and a dynamic solution is provided. Thus, the conceptual model is still that of reaches in series, but here the flow is modeled explicitly using the full-hydrodynamic equations and the advection dispersion equation is solved dynamically (Cox 2003).

MIKE 11 water quality module (ECO Lab) is the water quality module, which is an extension of the advection-dispersion module and is utilized to simulate the reaction processes of multi compound systems and models a variety of biochemical interaction processes, including BOD and DO computations and simulations of nutrients, macrophytes and plankton. The ECO Lab module solves the system of coupled differential equations describing the physical, chemical and biological interactions in the river (DHI 2012).

MIKE 11 is widely used to model hydrodynamic and water quality of rivers all over the world. MIKE 11 hydrodynamic model was used with the advection-dispersion module to simulate water temperature, dissolved oxygen, nitrogen and total dissolved gas in the Snake River, USA (Madsen et

al. 2001). Hydrodynamic and water quality MIKE 11 model was developed for simulation of the contaminant loadings of nitrate and phosphate to assess the water quality of Pasikhan River, Iran in 2011(Razdar et al. 2011). In 2012, Eisakhani et al. applied MIKE 11 to model the discharge, BOD and COD loads in each cross section of Bertam River in Malaysia (Eisakhani et al. 2012). In China, Liang J. et al developed MIKE 11 water quality model as a tool for evaluation of alternative water management scenarios for the Lao Hewan river basin of Beijing (Liang et al. 2015).

2.6 Previous Water Quality Studies for the Rosetta Branch

2.6.1 Water Quality Assessment Studies

Several studies have investigated the water quality status of the River Nile particularly for the Rosetta Branch (Abdo 2013; Agrama 2012; Alawy et al. 2015; Daifullah et al. 2003; Elewa et al. 2009; Ezzat et al. 2012; Khan et al. 2008; Mostafa and Peters 2016; Moustafa et al. 2010; Yousry et al. 2011).

Daifullah et al. (2003) studied the effect of heavy metals on the aquatic ecosystem of the Rosetta Branch particularly the result of waste disposal from (El-Malyia and Soda and Salts) companies into the branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. The results showed that the concentrations of heavy metals are higher than the permissible levels due to the discharges of two industrial companies. The treatment procedures using H-carbon showed that the percent removal of toxic metals almost reaches $\geq 97\%$ and in all cases the heavy metal concentration after treatment is less than the permissible level.

Khan et al. (2008) investigated a real time water quality monitoring network and water quality indices for the River Nile. 69 sites along the River Nile were monitored by the National Water Research Center (NWRC) for water

quality on a biannual basis during 2008. These sites are divided between the five main locations including 3 sites along the Rosetta Branch. Egyptian Water Quality Index (EWQI) was developed which is based on the Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment Water Quality Index (CCMEWQI). Real Time Water Quality Network (RTWQ) stations were successfully installed in selected sites. The results showed that The EWQI categories were “Fair” for drinking and irrigation while “Poor” and “Excellent” for aquatic and livestock, respectively in the stations along the Rosetta branch.

Elewa et al. (2009) studied the changes in the River Nile water quality at Delta Barrage especially along the Rosetta Branch. Eighteen water samples were collected during the seasons of the year 2003, from nine stations at two branches and four canals. Principal component analysis (PCA) was used to summarize the general trend and changes in chemical parameters using correlation matrix. The results showed that the River Nile at Delta Barrage has good water quality without any harmful risk as shown by its safe human usage. In long term, the Rosetta Branch will remain threatened by the increasing of human activities. El-Rahawy Drain represents the main source of pollution in the study area.

Moustafa et al. (2010) studied the assessment of water quality in Rosetta Branch from eight sampling stations through four successive cruises (spring 2008 to winter 2009). Statistical analysis was established such as, correlation coefficient matrix, multiple box and Whisker plot. The results showed that the Rosetta Branch is heavily polluted and it is becoming a collecting system for various types of wastes, especially at El Rahawy drain, Sabal Drain and several factories in Kafr El-Zayat city. The distribution of the major cations and anions recorded the highest values in cold season and the lowest during the hot high flow period. Dissolved oxygen is depleted completely in the

discharge point of El-Rahawy Drain, while COD, BOD and TDS increased sharply at this site. The concentration of heavy metals in water samples were in the order of Fe> Mn> Pb>Zn>Cu. Fe, Mn and Pb concentration exceeded the permissible limits, especially in winter.

Yousry et al. (2011) studied the assessment of the River Nile water quality including 3 sites along the Rosetta Branch using exploratory and cluster analysis. The available data were collected in the period 2000 – 2007 by the National Water Quality and Availability Management (NAWQAM) project. The results showed that all water quality parameters have mean values within the allowable limits (Egyptian standards of Law 48 / year 1982) except COD. Also total coliform recorded high values especially along the Rosetta Branch. Cluster analysis indicated that River Nile and its two branches are exposed to three types of pollutants, nutrients, organic and sewage pollutants.

Agrama (2012) studied the assessment of water quality in the Rosetta and Damietta branches and some canals in twelve governorates of Egypt using Statistical Water Quality Index (SWQI) during the period of years from 2002 to 2009. The results of SWQI indicated that Aswan governorate is less vulnerable to surface water quality deterioration, while Damietta governorate is high vulnerable. The results showed a deterioration of water quality northward while water quality improved with time. Also, statistical analysis of SWQI indicated that BOD is the most effective on SWQI value.

Ezzat et al. (2012) studied the seasonal variations of physical, chemical and biological characteristics to assess the water quality of about 120 km along the Rosetta branch and five main drains located on its sides, from upstream El-Rahawy drain up to downstream of Tala drain. The used water quality assessment approaches are based on the NSFQI and the correlation coefficient matrix. The analytical data results indicated that High

concentrations of NH_3 , TDS, EC, BOD, turbidity and low concentrations of DO were recorded from two seasons trips (summer 2010 and winter 2011). The NSFQI results showed that water quality is seasonally very bad in El-Rahawy drain outlet and bad for other sites. The major contributor parameter in the indices calculations was fecal coliform, exceeding permissible limits, particularly in winter season.

Abdo (2013) studied the pollutants effect in the aquatic environment of the Rosetta Branch. 40 water samples were collected during four successive seasons from 10 stations along the branch. Statistical analysis such as, standard deviation, coefficient variation and correlation coefficients revealed that the strong relationships among the studied parameters. The results showed that the high concentration values of EC, TS, Cl, SO_4 , NO_2 , NO_3 , NH_3 , PO_4 and TP were recorded at point's discharge of drains with branch.

Alawy et al. (2015) studied the impact of industrial wastewater on water quality status of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. 108 water samples were collected during the spring and autumn 2010 from 9 different regions along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El- Zayat industrial area. Chemical analyses of water samples showed Pb, Cd, Hg, P, NH_3 , and S exceeded the permissible limit. The distributions of these parameters at the study area are strongly affected by the industrial effluents produced from El-Mobidat, El-Malyia and Salt and Soda companies. The results show that the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat industrial area is heavily polluted and consequently harmful effects to the aquatic environment.

El-Amier et al (2015) studied the physical and chemical characteristics of water and sediment in the Rosetta Branch by dividing it into three sites: site 1 (from El-Qanater El-Khairia to Kom Hamada), site 2 (from Kom Hamada to Edfina) and site 3 (from Edfina to Rosetta). NSFQI was applied using

computer program, based on recorded parameters. Also, the one-way ANOVA and correlation analyses were conducted. The results of water parameters analyses showed highest significant correlations among three ecological sites, except pH and sulphates. It's noticeable that BOD and COD were recorded the highest concentrations in site 2, opposite to Kafr El-Zayat city. The NSFQI results indicated that site 2 is more polluted than the other two sites and water quality status is bad. The concentrations of heavy metals increase in sites that are more affected by drainage water from different drains.

Mostafa and Peters (2016) studied the assessment of water quality at the Rosetta Branch of the River Nile. 17 sampling stations were chosen along the Rosetta branch from upstream of the El-Rahawy drain to the end of the branch during four seasons 2013. The NSFQI was applied seasonally at different points. Also, statistical analysis approaches were performed using a two-way ANOVA (analysis of variance) and correlation matrix. The results of the physical-chemical analysis showed that the worst water quality conditions were recorded during winter and summer seasons. The fecal coliform is the main cause of poor water quality along the Rosetta branch. The results of NSFQI showed medium water quality upstream of the El-Rahawy and Tala drains and bad water quality downstream of those drains. The results of ANOVA testing showed the ranking of the drains in terms of their impact on the mass loading at the Rosetta branch is as follows: the El-Rahawy, the Tala, the Sabal, the El-Tahrir and the Zawyet El-Baher.

2.6.2 Water Quality Modeling Studies

Water quality modeling of the Rosetta Branch was developed in limited publications (Donia 2005; Donia et al. 2003; El-Bahrawy and Abu Elaa 2002;

El Gammal and El Shazely 2008; Mohamed 2008; Mohamed 2013; Mostafa 2014; Othman et al. 2009).

El-Bahrawy and Abu Elaa (2002) studied the effect of industrial wastes disposal on the water quality of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city using QUAL2EU model. The simulation exercise showed the importance of establishing a water quality model for the Nile River particularly for the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city that can be used for management purposes. The model should be recent enough and reflecting the state of art of water quality modeling.

Donia et al. (2003) investigated the water quality control of the Rosetta Branch, using DUFLOW simulation model, which was applied to simulate the water quality. The aim of the study is to predict the effect of proposed waste effluents on the downstream quality particularly for the drinking water plants. Economic and optimization models were developed to evaluate the cost associated with each treatment alternative and to decide the optimum degree of treatment for the wastes needed before discharging them into the water. The results showed that Rahway drain effluent is the major factor influencing the water quality of the Rosetta Branch and the optimum treatment of Rahway drain is the treatment using wetland option.

Donia (2005) developed DUFLOW waste load allocation model to define the total maximum daily loads for pollutants to assess the water quality of the Rosetta Branch. The evaluated model was calibrated successfully until an agreement was reached between the simulated and the measured data. Several scenarios were conducted using the developed model to improve the water quality condition of the Rosetta Branch. Based on the results of these scenarios, the total maximum daily loads were established for the Rosetta

Branch. Applications demonstrate that the developed model can be used by decision makers as a tool to quality management.

Mohamed (2008) studied the determination of the environmental pollution levels in water and sediment of Rosetta branch. Water quality model (DUFLOW) was developed to reduce the pollution along Rosetta branch. The results showed that, although the Rosetta Branch receives effluents from various sources of pollution, a considerable self-purification capability after kafr El-Zayat area was observed. The experimental results showed that the lowest values represent the reference point, which is far from any pollution source and is considered as the background concentration level. The highest concentrations were found in the area located downstream pollution sources especially downstream El-Rahawy and El-Malyia Company. Different scenarios using DUFLOW model indicated that the reduction of pollutants discharging from El-Rahawy drain by using wetland treatment technique leads to mitigate the pollution along Rosetta branch.

El Gammal and El Shazely (2008) studied different scenarios for water quality management in the Rosetta Branch during the low demand period using QUAL2K water quality model. Simulation of organic nitrogen and ammonia showed possible improvements in the Rosetta Branch due to applying source control strategies and in water control methods. The results showed that the impacts of high organic loads can be mitigated by releasing 30 Million Cubic Meter per day from River Nile water at the Delta Barrage. QUAL2K modeling proved that this solution reduced the concentrations of ammonia and organic nitrogen below the limits of the local guidelines. Also, 0.9 Billion Cubic Meter per day from the River Nile fresh water can be saved and the ammonium concentration is reduced to 70% in the low demands period by stopping the wastewater effluent discharges from Abo Rawash

WWTP to the Rosetta Branch. The authors suggested that the primary treated wastewater effluent can be diverted to the western desert to irrigate trees.

Othman (2009) studied the evaluation of the water quality in the southern part of the Rosetta branch. Different scenarios were applied during low and high flow periods using water quality model (QUAL2K) to mitigate the pollution along Rosetta branch. The results showed that EI-Rahawy drain considers as one of the most important sources of pollution along the Rosetta Branch and the area downstream EI-Rahawy drain is classified as medium to very bad quality. Also wetland model was applied to purify the water of EI-Rahawy drain. The output results showed good results in reducing of BOD concentrations and fecal coliform when applying wetland treatment technique.

Samia Mohamed (2013) studied the surface water quality management along the Rosetta Branch for three years 2004, 2006 and 2008. WASP7.4 water quality model was developed to simulate the water quality status. This model was calibrated and used to simulate different scenarios for improving the water quality of Rosetta Branch. The results showed that it is concluded that the main water quality problem in the Branch is due to the increasing of NH_3 and BOD above guidelines especially after the Rahawy and Tala drains. The scenarios results showed that the increasing of discharge in the branch does not affect the significant impact on the quality of water in the branch. While the improving of water quality for point sources effluents especially at El-Rahawy drain, will lead to improve the water quality in the Rosetta Branch.

Moustafa (2014) developed a model for simulating pollutant transport in the River Nile Delta and managing water quality in affected areas that has been created by using MATLAB software. Water quality assessment approaches

such as correlation matrix , analysis of variance and water quality index (WQI) have been applied in this study .The WQI showed that fecal coliform bacteria the main cause of poor water quality along the River Nile Delta. The results showed significant differences among the impacts of each pollution source on the water quality.

MIKE 11 was used to simulate the River Nile in limited publications (El-Sadek et al. 2011; Radwan 2009; Reda et al. 2015).

Radwan (2009) studied the effect of predicted global warming in terms of expected temperature rise on the water quality status in terms of DO for the Rosetta Branch in the Nile Delta of Egypt. The model aims to describe and predict concentrations of dissolved oxygen (DO), taking into consideration advection, dispersion and the most important biological, chemical and physical processes. The results indicated that global warming is likely to increase the stress on Rosetta branch and to decrease its water quality. Higher water temperatures reduce dissolved oxygen levels, especially for low concentrations (<5 mg/l) which may have a negative effect on the aquatic life. If this effect will be combined with reduction in stream flow, the deterioration of the quality status of the branch might be severe.

El-Sadek et al. (2011) developed MIKE 11 water quality model to simulate water quality status along the Rosetta Branch in the Nile Delta. All significant pollution sources along the Rosetta Branch were considered especially contamination from El-Moheet, Sabal, and Tala Drains. The model was calibrated and validated based on the available sampling data along the Branch. Given the data limitations for calculation of the model input and for model calibration, the simulation results can be considered good. This study focused on the model results for NO₃ and TDS, and links the results towards

their use in water management applying the combined HD-WQ model as integrated decision support tool. Decisions can be based on prior simulation of scenarios in the developed model.

Reda et al. (2015) developed MIKE11 water quality model to simulate water quality status along the River Nile, covers Cairo governorate, bounded by El Saff town at Km 877.00 from the South and El Kanater town at Km 953.00 from the North. The model was calibrated and validated to simulate different scenarios for improving water quality problems. The hydraulic and water quality parameters upstream Cairo drinking water plants were successfully simulated using data sets of three successive years (2012, 2013 and 2014). Three water quality parameters (DO, BOD and COD) were modeled. The management scenarios showed that the maximum water quality improvement can be achieved under integrated management approach of study reach water quality based on the application of drain effluent treatment, drinking water plant sludge disposal treatment and increasing the study reach flow.

2.7 Research Deficits and Demands for this Study

The water quality status of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city was evaluated in the previous studies based on the records of one station, which is located next to or before the industrial zone. The effects of the Tala Drain and the industrial zone discharges were not investigated in details. In this research work, the study area is subjected to these two different sources of pollution in short distance. An intensive analysis of the water quality status of this study area has been done using two different water quality indices. Moreover, a hydrodynamic and water quality model for the study area has been developed to manage its water quality, based on enhancement scenarios.

Chapter (3)

STUDY AREA & MONITORING PROGRAM

The study area, the sampling procedure, the experimental work, the developing of the study area bathymetry, analysis of monitoring results and ecological analysis will be described and discussed in this chapter.

3.1 Study Area

The study area covers about 3 km stretch of the Rosetta Branch. It is located between Al-Gharbiyah and El-Behira Governorates at Kafr El-Zayat city, ($30^{\circ} 48' 55''$ N, $30^{\circ} 48' 23''$ E), as shown in Figure (3-1). It starts at the downstream of Kafr El-Zayat Highway Bridge and extends to the downstream of the industrial area of Kafr El Zayat city. The study area includes two main sources of pollution; the Tala Drain and three industrial companies (El-Mobidat Company, El-Malyia Company and Salt and Soda Company) at Kafr El Zayat city. Tala Drain is the main source of pollution in the study area of this research work. It is considered as the second major source of pollution along the Rosetta Branch after the EL-Rahawy Drain (Mostafa 2014). The Tala Drain flows from the middle of the Nile Delta with a total length of about 39.5 km to discharge to the Rosseta Branch at kafr El-Zayat city (about 121 Km northern to the Delta Barrages).The Tala Drain is mainly polluted by agricultural drainage, domestic wastewater and industrial wastewater from chemical and dairy industry, which are located along its path. The average flow at the Tala drain is about 450,000 m³/day. Three villages (El- Shohada, El-Batanoon and Tabkooha) daily discharge more than

200,000 m³ of its raw sewage to the Tala drain (Mostafa 2015). The dairy industry generates about 5500 m³ of wastewater every year. The Tala drain receives also about 250,000 m³ of agricultural drainage water every day. The discharge of Tala Drain is about 0.87 million m³/day into the Rosetta Branch. It serves 137,000 Feddan of the very fertile old lands, and has 11 branches which carry the drainage water from the agricultural land to the main drain (Mohamed 2013).

Figure (3-1): The location of the study area (modified after (MWRI 2005))

Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city is influenced by the industrial companies (at a distance of about 123 Km northern to the Delta Barrages), which directly discharge their chemical effluents without any treatment

(Abdo 2013). These industrial outfalls are El-Mobidat (pesticides and chemical company); El-Malyia (fertilizer production company); and Salt and Soda company (Alawy et al. 2015). The Rosetta Branch is mainly used for drinking purpose, many drinking water plants and water intake stations for some towns are directly located after the study area such as, Benofor intake (at a distance of about 124 Km from the Delta Barrages) and Abieg intake (at a distance of about 134 Km from the Delta Barrages), Figure (3-2) (Mohamed 2008).

Figure (3-2): Different pollution sources and drinking water plants along Rosetta Branch

3.2 Monitoring System

The main objective of this research work is the water quality management of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. For that, water quality monitoring program was organized, including each key site of Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-

Zayat city. Monitoring system is based on field sampling and laboratory tests to secure water quality records for the study area. Thirty-two water samples were collected from the eight monitoring stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city and from the outlet of Tala Drain. These samples were collected for one year every three months during different seasons starting from the autumn of 2014 to the summer of 2015.

3.2.1 Hydrological Characteristics

Figures (3-3) and (3-4) show the water level records of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city and the discharge of Rosetta Branch downstream the Delta Barrages, respectively, for one year during the period from October 2014 to October 2015. These field records were recorded by the Egyptian Ministry of Water Resources and Irrigation (MWRI 2015).

Figure (3-3): Water levels of Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city from Oct. 2014 to Oct. 2015 (MWRI 2015)

Figure (3-4): Discharge records of Rosetta Branch downstream the Delta Barrages from Oct. 2014 to Oct. 2015 (MWRI 2015).

3.2.2 Sampling Stations

Eight stations were selected along the study area to cover the different environmental conditions of water in the Rosetta Branch, seven of them along the Rosetta Branch and the eighth is located at the outlet of the Tala Drain, Figure (3-5). Stations S1, S2, S4, S5 and S8 are assigned as major sampling stations, while station S3, S6 and S7 are assigned as minor sampling stations (less water quality tests).

Figure (3-5): Location of the sampling stations (modified after Google Earth)

Station (S2) represents a pollution point source of the Tala Drain, which receives discharge from dairy industry, agricultural drainage and untreated domestic wastewater. Station (S5) represents a pollution point source of the downstream of the industrial companies. Stations coordinates were estimated using a GPS equipment (Garmin GPSMAP 78s), Table (3-1). The locations of the stations were selected based on the significant activities on the branch in the study area.

Table (3-1): Locations and description of the selected stations

Station code	Description	Location	
		Longitude (x) East	Latitude (y) North
S1	At Kafr El-Zayat Highway Bridge	30° 48.55'	30° 48.95'
S2	At the outlet of Tala Drain	30° 48.98'	30° 48.88'
S3	At Kafr El-Zayat Railway Bridge	30° 48.69'	30° 49.15'
S4	Upstream the industrial companies by 500 m	30° 48.55'	30° 49.46'
S5	Downstream the industrial companies by 500 m	30° 47.86'	30° 49.72'
S6	In front of Tala drain's outlet	30° 48.66'	30° 49.06'
S7	Downstream Kafr El-Zayat Railway Bridge by 250 m	30° 48.70'	30° 49.33'
S8	At the outlet of the industrial companies	30° 48.20'	30° 49.69'

3.2.3 Water Quality Sampling & Testing

Cleaned polyethylene and glasses bottles were used for samples collecting at a depth of 0.3 m under the water surface according to (APHA 2005). The samples were collected from the middle section of the branch except for two stations, S2 at the outlet of the Tala Drain and S8 at the outlet of the industrial companies of Kafr El Zayat city. Water samples were placed into

an ice chest for transportation to the laboratory, as shown in Figure (3-6). Testing of the water samples occurred no later than 2 days after their collection as a mean of avoiding microbiological decomposition of solids. Water samples were analyzed for different parameters during the winter, spring, summer, and autumn seasons.

Figure (3-6): The used Bottles for sampling inside icebox

3.2.3.1 Sampling technique

According to the decision of the Minister of Irrigation (No. 92 for the year 2013), the executive regulations of the Law No. 48 of 1982, regarding the River Nile and waterways from pollution protection, sampling procedure and experimental analysis are controlled by Articles 45, 46 and 47 as following:

- The sample size should not less than two liters for chemical analysis and one liter for bacteriological analysis. Samples are collected in glass bottles with sealed lid and must clean inside the pot and cover

well before use. In case of bacteriological analysis, samples are collected in sterile containers and it is necessary to follow the approved standard methods in (APHA 2005).

- In the case of a delay in scheduled tests for more than three hours, one needs to save the samples inside of an ice box, briefing the containers with a layer of ice up to arrive samples to the laboratory and taking into account the precautions in (APHA 2005).
- The samples must be representative of the nature of the liquid waste as much as possible and in the place where the act it into waterways. In the case of chemical analysis, bottles should be filled completely and put the stopper after the completion of sampling tightly. It should not be allowed to remain any bubble of gas, filled between surface of the water and the stopper in bottles. In the case of bacteriological analysis, space should be leaved in the top third of the bottle. Bottle nozzle is placed reverse the direction of water flow.

3.2.3.2 Monitoring water quality parameters

Water samples from eight monitoring stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city and from the Tala Drain, were seasonally analyzed for 18 water quality parameters during the four seasons.

The measured parameters are: 3 physical parameters; 13 chemical parameters and 2 biological parameters, as shown in Figure (3-7).

Figure (3-7): Measured water quality parameters

The choice of number and type of parameters depends on four factors: the previous studies; the weight of parameters; the availability of water quality equipment and the used water quality indices. Multiple water quality equipment have been used to measure and analyze these parameters both on site or in the laboratories; the Laboratory of the Irrigation and Hydraulics Engineering Department, Faculty of Engineering, Tanta University and the laboratory of the Water Supply and Sewerage Company at Gharbiya Governorate in Tanta city.

3.2.4 Water Quality Equipment

Table (3-2) summarizes the equipment, which were used to measure eighteen water quality parameters and the locality of sampling procedure.

Table (3-2): A summary of measured parameters and the used equipment

Parameters	Unit	Equipment	Site
Water temperature	°C	YSI Professional Plus Multi Parameter	In-Site
TDS	mg/l		
pH			
DO	mg/l		
Salinity	ppt		
EC	µS		
PO ₄ , SO ₄ NO ₂ , NO ₃ Cl ⁻ , Fe, Mn	mg/l	YSI 9300 Photometer	The Laboratory of the Irrigation and Hydraulics Engineering Department
Turbidity	NTU	Turbidity Meter	
BOD	mg/l	Standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater American Public Health Association (APHA 2005)	The Laboratory of the Water Supply and Sewerage Company at Gharbiya Governorate
COD	mg/l		
Fecal coliform	N/100 ml		
Total algae	N/ml		

3.2.4.1 YSI Professional Plus Multi Parameter

YSI Professional Plus Multi Parameter, Figure (3-8), is a water quality instrument that measures some physical and chemical parameters. It provides extreme flexibility for the measurement of a variety of combinations for

dissolved oxygen, conductivity, specific conductance, salinity, resistivity, total dissolved solids (TDS), pH, ORP, pH/ORP combination, ammonium (ammonia), nitrate, chloride and temperature. A detailed description of the equipment components, theory of operation and utilization method can be found in YSI Professional Plus Multiparameter Water Quality Meter User Manual (YSI Professional Plus 2010).

The YSI Professional Plus Multi Parameter consists of:

1. Backlit display and keypad.
2. Rubber over-molded.
3. Adjustable hand strap.
4. MS rugged connector.
5. Rugged and durable field cable (30m).
6. Multiple sensor options (3 Sensors: temperature/conductivity, DO and pH).

Figure (3-8): YSI Professional Plus Multi Parameter

3.2.4.2 YSI 9300 Photometer

YSI 9300, Figure (3-9), is a water quality equipment that is suitable for use in both the laboratory and the field. The YSI photometers are instruments that measure color intensity. Light is passed through a test tube containing the sample solution, and then through a colored filter onto a photodetector. Filters have been chosen so that light of a specific wavelength is selected. When the solution is completely colorless, all of the light passes through the sample. With colored samples, light is absorbed and the light which passes through the sample is proportionately reduced. In the following test procedures, the photometer is used to measure the color which is produced when chemical reagents are reacted with the water sample. The photometer is pre-programmed with calibrations for each test parameter. The detailed formulation of the equipment components, theory of operation and utilization method is described in YSI 9300 Photometer User Manual (YSI 9300 Direct-Read Photometers 2010). The YSI 9300 Photometer consists of:

1. Backlit graphic display.
2. Test tubes.
3. Reagent for each parameter.

Figure (3-9): YSI 9300 Photometer

3.2.4.3 Turbidity Meter

Turbidity Meter, Figure (3-10), is an equipment for measuring turbidity. It is easily portable for use in the field or laboratory; it is very accurate, and especially useful for measuring very low turbidities. It is used to determine the concentration of suspended particles in a sample of water by measuring the incident light scattered at right angles from the sample. NTU (Nephelometric Turbidity Unit) is its measuring unit. The range of measurement ranges from 0 to 100 NTU. A detailed description of the equipment components, theory of operation and utilization method can be found in (Turbidity Meter User Manual TU 2016).

Turbidity Meter consists of:

1. Turbidity Meter body with display screen.
2. Testing bottle with 0 NTU standard solution.
3. Testing bottle with 100 NTU standard solution.
4. Two empty testing bottle.
5. Clean Solution (Distill Water).

Figure (3-10): Turbidity Meter

3.2.5 Developing of Study Area Bathymetry

One of the main objectives of this work is to develop a hydrodynamic and ecological model for the Rosetta Branch. In order to achieve this, a topographical survey for the bed of the branch (bathymetry) should be provided. The Lowrance Elite-5 Sonar/GPS equipment was used for this survey. The equipment was installed on a fishing boat to properly function. The transducer of Elite-5 Sonar must be installed in the water all the time and in a location that has a smooth flow of water when the boat is moving. The boat was moving on a zigzag shape. The readings were approximately recorded every 20 meters to cover the study area, as can be seen in Figure (3-11).

Figure (3-11): Bathymetry recording stations for the study area

Finally, a GIS database was developed to arrange, manage and present the spatial distribution of collected data. GIS database schema is established for 680 recording stations in the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. Using the Inverse Distance Weighted (IDW) technique, twenty-four cross sections along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city have been extracted to develop the hydrodynamic and water quality model, check Figure (3-12).

The results of all cross sections can be seen in Appendix (B).

Figure (3-12): Developed bathymetry and bed levels of the study area using GIS

- Lowrance Elite-5 Sonar/GPS

The Lowrance Elite 5 Sonar, Figure (3-13), is an equipment that features a five hundred watt RMS sounder that reaches depths of up to one thousand feet below the water surface. It is used to measure water depth and bed level

of the study area. It has accurate internal GPS antenna that is used to estimate points coordinates. The detailed formulation of the equipment components, theory of operation and utilization method is described in Lowrance Elite 5 Sonar/GPS User Manual (Lowrance Elite 2010).

Lowrance Elite 5 Sonar consists of:

1. Mounting display unit.
2. External GPS port.
3. Wire.
4. Battery 12V.
5. Transducer (sensor).

Figure (3-13): Elite-5 Sonar/GPS

3.3 Analysis of Monitoring Records

Water samples from eight monitoring stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city and from the Tala Drain, were seasonally collected and analyzed during the period from November 2014 to August 2015. The records were compared to the Egyptian water quality standards for fresh waterways, decree No. 49 – Law 48/1982 – Article No. 60 amended in 2013, Table (3-3).

Table (3-3): Egyptian water quality standards for surface waterways (decree No. 49/2013 – Law 48/1982)

No.	Parameters (units)	Objectives
1	Water temperature change (degrees C)	+5°C
2	Turbidity (NTU)	0-100
3	pH	6.5 - 8.5
4	DO (mg/l)	> 6
5	BOD (mg/l)	< 6
6	COD (mg/l)	< 10
7	TDS (mg/l)	< 500
8	NO ₃ (mg/l)	< 2
9	SO ₄ (mg/l)	< 200
10	Fe (mg/l)	< 0.5
11	Mn (mg/l)	< 0.2

3.3.1 Water Quality Parameters

The records of measured physical, chemical and biological water quality parameters at the different stations in the study area are presented in the Figures from (3-14) to (3-31). Moreover, the boxplot statistical method was used to describe the water quality parameters as can be seen in the presented figures. Boxplots were carried out using SPSS version 20.0.

The boxplot is a very useful and concise graphical display for summarizing the distribution of a data, as shown in Figure (3-13). Box plots are an excellent tool for conveying location and variation information in data sets, particularly for detecting and illustrating location and variation changes between different groups of data (Navidi 2010). Box plots provide visual summaries of the centre of the data (the median), the variation or spread (the box height), the skewness and the presence or absence of unusual values (outliers and extreme values) (Chambers 1983).

Figure (3-14): The description of boxplot

3.3.1.1 Physical parameters

Water Temperature

Figure (3-15) shows the spatial distribution of water temperature for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). The obtained values of the water temperature parameter recorded 14.7, 21.7, 28.3 and 32.8 °C in winter, autumn, spring and summer, respectively, with no thermal pollution above

the permissible limits (Law 48/1982). In the present study, water temperature showed noticeable seasonal trends with a lowest value (14.7°C) recorded during winter and a highest value (32.8°C) during summer at all considered stations. The changes of water temperature depend on the variations in meteorological condition, time of sampling, air temperature, back radiation and latent heat of evaporation and seasons. On the other hand, bacteria and other microorganisms which affect on the breakdown of organic matter at the Tala drain (Station No.2) are very much influenced by temperature changes. Consequently, they are more active during summer than winter. This observation was agreed with that reported by (Tayel et al. 2008). Moreover, a significant rise in the water temperatures during summer affects negatively on the different chemical parameters, in particular the dissolved oxygen.

Figure (3-15): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of water temperature at the different sampling stations in the study area

Turbidity

Figure (3-16) shows the spatial distribution of turbidity for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). The average obtained values of the turbidity recorded 22.28, 26.12, 34.1 and 31.23 NTU at the considered

stations along the Rosetta Branch in autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The maximum value recorded at Station No.3 (S3) in spring (39.67 NTU) due to discharge from the Tala drain. Station No. 2 (S2), which represents the Tala drain outlet, the values ranged from 23 to 37.6 NTU. The high values of turbidity, recorded in spring (37.6 NTU), may be attributed to the increase in the uptake of suspended mater by phytoplankton and increased solar radiation penetrating the surface water as well as settling out of suspended particles to the bottom sediments. Results showed variation in turbidity values according to pollution extent and suspended particles. Data reveals that the highest values were in spring and summer while the lowest ones were in autumn and winter. In general, the high values in turbidity may be related to the decreasing viscosity of the water with increasing of the temperature, increasing of the bacterial activity and the discharge of heavily polluted effluent loaded with agriculture, industrial, and domestic wastes. This observation was agreed with that reported by (Saad et al. 2011).

Figure (3-16): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of turbidity at the different sampling stations in the study area

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

Figure (3-17) shows the spatial distribution of total dissolved solids for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). Generally, the majority of records for all stations along the Rosetta Branch were within the permissible limits (Law 48/1982) except during autumn, TDS records 630, 540 and 530 mg/l at S7, S4 and S5, respectively. The main reason for increasing TDS may be due to agricultural and residential runoff, leaching of soil contamination and point source water pollution discharge from industrial and sewage wastewater. For station No. 2 (S2), which represents the Tala Drain, the TDS concentrations ranged from 988 mg/l to 1137 mg/l, which are higher than the maximum permissible limit of TDS (500 mg/l according to Law 48/1982). High concentration of TDS in the samples of this station is due to seepage from unlined sewage lines, domestic wastewater, agricultural fertilizer and leachates from waste dumps in the Tala drain.

Figure (3-17): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of TDS at the different sampling stations in the study area

3.3.1.2 Chemical parameters

pH

Figure (3-18) shows the spatial distribution of pH for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). The pH records of collected samples ranged from 7.22 to 7.8 in all seasons except in spring. These values are within the permissible limits of law 48/1982 (6.5-8.5). The highest alkaline value (9.6) was recorded in spring at Station No.7. The pH records in spring at Stations No. 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 are higher than the maximum permissible limit of pH (8.5 according to Law 48/1982), its average is about 9.2. Decrease in pH values of the Tala drain (S2) may be due to that this drain is municipal sewer that contains large quantities from organic and gets oxidized by bacteria decomposition.

The average values of pH in different seasons indicate that the highest value was in spring while the lowest one was in summer, pH value decreased in summer of higher temperature due to CO₂ and H₂S gases that liberated during decomposition of organic matter by bacteria as reported by (Abdel-Satar 2005).

The increase of pH values in spring could be related to photosynthesis and growth of aquatic plants (dense vegetation and phytoplankton). Photosynthesis consumes carbon dioxide (CO₂) leading to the rise of pH value as reported by (Abdel-Satar 2005). Generally, the pH values below 6.5 and higher than 9.0 is harmless to fish, although the toxicity of other poisons may be affected by the changes within this range as reported by (Ahmed 2012). The boxplot of pH showed that there are four samples that the pH values were out of the trend of other samples in the spring.

Figure (3-18): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of pH at the different sampling stations in the study area

Dissolved Oxygen (DO)

Figure (3-19) shows the spatial distribution of dissolved oxygen for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). It can be noticed that the average value of DO concentrations recorded 5.93, 6.36, 8.61 and 1.33 mg/l at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch in autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. DO concentrations showed that the highest values were recorded in spring while the lowest ones were recorded in summer. This might be related to the rapid wind speed in spring and the decrease in the water temperature than summer. Also, increasing DO concentration during spring season is because cold water absorbs more oxygen than warm water, more sunlight penetrates the water, and phytoplankton reproduces rapidly, as reported by (Abdel-Satar and Elewa 2001).

Figure (3-19): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of DO at the different sampling stations in the study area

During autumn, Station No.1 (S1) has the maximum value of DO concentrations (12.3 mg/l) due to this station represent the upstream of the study area and the sampling location before the outlet of the Tala drain. On the other hand, the increase of DO at (S1) may be due to the high solubility of oxygen at low water temperature, the activities of wind action and air movement which allow more transfer of oxygen across the air-water interface as well as increase of photosynthetic activity by phytoplankton, as reported by (Ahmed 2007). The observed record of DO in summer, in the Tala Drain (S2) recorded the lowest record for this study, 0.26 mg/l. thus, exerting a direct impact on the other stations along the Rosetta Branch in the study area which ranged from 1.07 to 1.7 mg/l. These values were far below standards of law 48/1982 (>6 mg/l) and might indicate high organic matter and nutrients load from the discharge of agricultural drainage and domestic wastewater in the Tala Drain. Waste discharges high in organic matter and nutrients can lead to decreases in DO concentrations as a result of the

increased microbial activity (respiration) occurring during the degradation of the organic matter, as reported by (El-Gamal and Shafik 1985).

Generally the DO values at most selected stations of the Rosetta branch and Tala Drain are within the permissible limits of law 48/1982 except for the summer season. DO values were greatly affected by pollution load where the lowest DO value recorded at stations located downstream Tala Drain. This is due to the excessive effluent discharge with high load of organic matter into the Rosetta Branch lead to deoxygenation of water. The highest value of DO recorded at station (S1) located upstream Tala drain, which recorded high DO value. The increasing of DO contents is attributed to the high rate of biosynthesis of oxygen, penetration of light energy accompanied by the uptake of inorganic carbon and carbohydrates by utilization of CO₂ as reported by (El-Sayed 2011).

The decrease in DO concentration may be due to the increase of the water temperature and the phytoplankton blooming in the summer. The depletion in DO may be due to dissolved oxygen exhaustion for oxidation of huge organic matter discharged into the Rosetta Branch, as reported by (Saad et al. 2011). At the outlet of the Tala Drain, the depletion of DO may be due to the presence of high load of the organic pollutants and nutrients that consumes the dissolved oxygen during oxidation processes especially during summer, as reported by (Mahmoud et al. 2008).

Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD)

Figure (3-20) shows the spatial distribution of biochemical oxygen demand for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). It can be noticed that the average value of BOD concentrations recorded 13.25, 3.5, 4.25 and 6.5

mg/l at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch in autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The highest value was in autumn season while the lowest one was in winter. During autumn, all station showed higher values, (ranged from 11 mg/l to 16 mg/l) far above the standard limits of law 48/1982 (< 6 mg/l). Station No.5 (S5), which represents the downstream of the industrial area, has the maximum value of BOD (16 mg/l) along the Rosetta Branch during autumn.

Figure (3-20): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of BOD at the different sampling stations in the study area

All BOD records at Station No.2 (S2) are higher than the maximum permissible limit (6 mg/l) during different seasons. The high value of BOD may be attributed to the presence of high load of discharged wastes (agricultural and sewage) into the Tala drain.

The BOD records along the Rosetta Branch and at the Tala Drain outlet at Kafr El-Zayat city violate the standard limits of law 48 (6 mg/l) at most stations especially during the autumn. The high records of BOD at other considered stations along the Rosetta Branch next to Tala Drain outlet, this

may be attributed to the decomposition of high amount of organic matter by microorganisms which increased by the rise of water temperature (El-Sayed 2011). The high BOD concentrations at S1 (11 mg/l) in autumn is related to the same reason but due to other drains along the branch by to the Tala Drain (from the El-Rahawy and Sabal Drain). The increase in BOD values at most investigation stations along the Rosetta Branch especially S4, S5 and S8 reflect the high load of organic matter discharged into Rosetta branch which receive high amounts of sewage, domestic, agricultural and industrial wastes from the outlet of the Tala Drain and Kafr El-Zayat companies, this observation agrees with that obtained by (Osman et al. 2010).

Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)

Figure (3-21) shows the spatial distribution of chemical oxygen demand for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). It can be noticed that the average value of COD concentrations recorded 26.75, 27.5, 27 and 26.5 mg/l at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch in autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. All records of COD concentrations in the study area exceeded the standard limits of law 48/1982 (10 mg/l). This is may be attributed to organic substances in the study area which are mainly produced by the decomposition of domestic wastes, planktonic organisms, and particulate organic matter discharged through the Tala drain into the Rosetta Branch and chemical wastes from industrial companies at Kafr El-Zayat city. These results are accordance in the same branch with that reported by (Abdo 2013) on the same branch.

Figure (3-21): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of COD at the different sampling stations in the study area

All COD records at Station No.2 (S2) are higher than the maximum permissible limit (10 mg/l) during different seasons. S2 has the maximum value of COD concentrations (38 mg/l) during the spring. The high value of COD may be attributed to the presence of higher organic matter concentration in these areas. This may be due to the discharge of industrial effluents into the Tala Drain by some non-compliant factories in these areas, in addition to the discharge of municipal wastewater (untreated and detergent-carrying wastewater) and other wastes into the Tala Drain.

For Station No.5 (S5), which represents the downstream of the industrial area, COD values varied from 36 mg/l to 28 mg/l during autumn and summer, respectively. The higher value of COD during summer may be attributed to the increase in water temperature which accelerates the oxidation of organic matter and decrease in oxygen content, as well as high load of organic matter and the low capacity of its water for self-purification in the autumn, this observation agrees with that obtained by (Abdo 2013).

Salinity

Figure (3-22) shows the spatial distribution of salinity for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). The obtained data showed that the lowest value of salinity, which is 0.2 ppt, was recorded at all stations along the Rosetta Branch during summer. On the other hand, the highest value of salinity was 0.82 ppt at S2 during autumn and winter. Concerning the difference in salinity values of water samples in different seasons, the highest values were recorded in autumn while the lowest ones were recorded in summer. The increasing in salinity values may be attributed to domestic wastewater and agricultural fertilizer that Tala drain are receiving large quantities of them, the evaporation rates, the seawater intrusion in low discharge seasons, as reported by (Elewa and El Nahry 2009). The solubility of oxygen decreases as temperature and salinity increase. So, it can be noticed that the value of DO concentrations are low, (Figure 3-18) with high salinity concentrations in S2 during the summer.

Figure (3-22): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of plot of salinity at the different sampling stations in the study area

Electrical Conductivity (EC)

Figure (3-23) shows the spatial distribution of electrical conductivity for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). The obtained data showed that the lowest value of EC is 471 μS at station No. 6 (S6) along the Rosetta Branch during summer, respectively. The decreasing in EC values may be attributed to the increase of water level during flood period and the uptake of dissolved salts by phytoplankton. The highest value of EC is 1680 μS at station No.2 during winter. The increasing in EC values may be attributed to the intrusion of the Tala drain's effluents into the lowered level water in the branch causing the rise of dissolved and suspended particles which increase the ability to convey electrical current, as reported by (El-Sayed 2011).

Figure (3-23): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of plot lot of EC at the different sampling stations in the study area

The increase in EC values were recorded during winter is mainly attributed to the increase in cations and anions concentrations of the water, as result of low water level and discharge But, the decrease in EC during summer may be due to the sedimentation of suspended solid with organic salts causing decrease in chemical elements concentration, as reported by (Abdo et al. 2010).

Generally, the high values of EC may be attributed to domestic and agricultural wastes that contain high amount of organic and inorganic constituents.

The results of EC (Figure 3-22), salinity (Figure 3-22) and TDS (Figure 3-16) show that the Tala drainage water is slightly saline. The increase and the magnitude of differences in EC values reflected the increase in soluble salts, cations and anions in the outlet of the Tala drain, comparing with the Rosetta Branch upstream water as reported by (Ghallab 2000).

Phosphate (PO₄)

Figure (3-24) shows the spatial distribution of phosphate for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). The average PO₄ concentrations were fluctuated between 2.15, 1.48, 0.89 and 0.34 mg/l at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch in autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The highest values were recorded in autumn while the lowest ones were recorded in summer. It can be noticed that PO₄ concentrations were increased at stations received and affected by organic pollution resulting from sewage, domestic, agricultural of the Tala drain and chemical effluents of industrial companies at Kafr El-Zayat city along the Rosetta Branch.

Station No. 8 (S8), which represents the outlet of industrial companies at Kafr El-Zayat city, has the maximum value of PO₄ concentrations (2.5 mg/l) during the autumn. It may be attributed to the chemical effluents of Kafr El-Zayat industrial area, which include the industrial effluents from the factories of superphosphate compounds, oil and soap industries and pesticides factories, as reported by (Daboor 2006).

There are no specific guidelines for phosphates in freshwater bodies. However, Law 48/1982 has specified that drains should have phosphates concentrations below 1 mg/l before the drainage water is pumped to a freshwater body. At Station No. 2 (S2), which represents the Tala Drain, the concentrations of PO_4 were recorded as: 2.8, 3.6, 1.85 and 2.3 mg/l in autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. These values exceed the permissible limit of PO_4 (1 mg/l). The increasing in PO_4 values may be attributed to domestic wastewater and agricultural fertilizer that Tala drain is receiving large quantities of them. This reflecting the effect of drainage water, sewage and agriculture is a major contributor of phosphorus to receiving waters, as reported by (Mohamed and Gad 2008).

Figure (3-24): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of PO_4 at the different sampling stations in the study area

Sulfate (SO_4)

Figure (3-25) shows the spatial distribution of sulfate for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). The average SO_4 concentrations were fluctuated between 90, 70, 57 and 73 mg/l at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch in autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The

highest values were recorded in autumn while the lowest ones were recorded in spring. All records of SO_4 concentrations in the study area didn't exceed the standard limits of law 48/1982 (200 mg/l), therefore they don't represent a risk to the environmental.

Figure (3-25): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of SO_4 at the different sampling stations in the study area

The obtained data showed that the highest value of sulfate at Tala drain outlet (S2) is 195 mg/l and 190 mg/l during spring and summer, respectively, while along the Rosetta Branch (at S6) is 190 mg/l and 180 mg/l during autumn and summer, respectively. The increasing in SO_4 values may be attributed to industrial wastewater from chemical and dairy industry, which is located along the Tala drain, as reported by (Ezzat et al. 2012)

Nitrite (NO_2)

Figure (3-26) shows the spatial distribution of nitrite for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). The average NO_2 concentrations were fluctuated between 0.11, 0.03, 0.08 and 0.09 mg/l at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch in autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The highest values were recorded in autumn while the lowest ones were

recorded in winter. The maximum values were recorded 0.135 and 0.27 mg/l at stations (S5) and (S8), respectively, during autumn. Station No.8 and Station No.5 are representing the outlet of the industrial area and the downstream of it at Kafr El-Zayat City, which directly discharge a great amount of chemical wastes, as reported by (Sayed 2003).

Figure (3-26): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of NO_2 at the different sampling stations in the study area

The NO_2 values were fluctuated from 0.125 to 0.5 mg/l at Tala drain outlet (S2) during summer and spring, respectively. The low values of nitrite during summer might be attributed to the fast conversion of NO_2 by nitrobacteria to NO_3 . On the other hand, the high nitrite level during spring may be attributed to the decomposition of organic matter present in the waste water where, nitrosomonas bacteria oxidize ammonia to nitrite by denitrification process, as reported by (Saad et al. 2011). Generally, natural water have small concentrations of nitrates and increase with runoff from agricultural lands (especially intensively cultivated lands with large inputs of synthetic fertilizers) and urban waste water, creating eutrophication, as reported by (Metawea 2009).

Nitrate (NO₃)

Figure (3-27) shows the spatial distribution of nitrate for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). All records of NO₃ concentrations in the study area didn't exceed the standard limits of law 48/1982 (2 mg/l), therefore they don't represent a risk to the environmental. The average NO₃ concentrations were ranged between 0.5, 0.48, 0.55 and 0.57 mg/l at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch in autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The low values of nitrate might be attributed to the uptake of nitrate by natural phytoplankton and its reduction by denitrifying bacteria and biological denitrification, as reported by (Saad et al., 2011)

Figure (3-27): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of NO₃ at the different sampling stations in the study area

The highest values were recorded in summer while the lowest ones were recorded in winter. The maximum values recorded 1 mg/l at stations (S3) and (S8) during spring and summer, respectively. The increase in NO₃ during spring and summer might be attributed to low consumption by phytoplankton

as well as the oxidation of ammonia by nitrifying bacteria and biological nitrification, as reported by (Sayed 2003).

All values were 1 mg/l at Tala drain outlet (S2) during different seasons. The increase of nitrate levels might be attributed to sewage wastes at Tala drain and low consumption of phytoplankton as well as the oxidation of ammonia by nitrosomonas bacteria and biological nitrification, as reported by (Abdo, 2010). Generally, Nitrate showed high values than the corresponding values of nitrite due to the fast conversion of NO_2 to NO_3 ions by nitrifying bacteria, as reported by (Abdel-Satar et al. 2010).

Chloride (Cl)

Figure (3-28) shows the spatial distribution of chloride for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). The average Cl concentrations were ranged between 269, 146, 252 and 210 mg/l at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch in autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The highest values were recorded in autumn while the lowest ones were recorded in winter.

Figure (3-28): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of Cl at the different sampling stations in the study area

Station No.5 (S5), which represents the downstream of the industrial area, has the maximum value of Cl concentrations (450 mg/l) along the Rosetta Branch during spring. At Tala drain outlet (S2), the values of Cl concentrations were ranged between 180 and 390 mg/l during winter and autumn, respectively. The increase in Cl concentrations at stations, Tala drain outlet (S2) and the downstream of industrial area (S5), during spring and autumn could be attributed to the domestic, agricultural drainage at (S2) and industrial effluents at (S5). The present results agreed with the findings of (Abdel-Satar and Elewa 2001) and (Sayed 2003) on the same area.

Iron (Fe)

Figure (3-29) shows the spatial distribution of iron for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat City for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). The concentrations of iron varied between 0.001 and 0.08 mg/l with the highest value at Station (S8) and the lowest value at Station (S2). All records of Fe concentrations in the study area did not exceed the standard limits of law 48/1982 (0.5 mg/l). The results showed slightly decrease of Fe due to the oxidation and precipitation of Fe on the bottom sediment, as reported by (Osman and Kloas 2010).

Figure (3-29): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of Fe at the different sampling stations in the study area.

Manganese (Mn)

Figure (3-30) shows the spatial distribution of manganese for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat City for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). The concentrations of manganese varied between 0.001 and 0.012 mg/l with the highest value at Station (S8) and the lowest value at Station (S1). All records of Mn concentrations in the study area did not exceed the standard limits of law 48/1982 (0.2 mg/l). Generally, the low levels of Mn may be due to the oxidation and precipitation of Mn on the bottom sediment, as reported by (Osman and Kloas 2010).

Figure (3-30): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of Mn at the different sampling stations in the study area

The values of heavy metals such as (Fe, Mn) were among recommended limits. These results may be due to the short half-lives of trace elements in the dissolved form because of their rapid transport of the sediments. The distribution of these metals is strongly affected by the chemical effluents produced from companies at Kafr El-Zayat which directly discharge industrial effluents at this area without any treatment. The present results agreed with the findings of (Daifullah et al. 2003) and (Abdo 2013) on the same study area.

3.3.1.3 Biological parameters

Fecal Coliform (FC)

Figure (3-31) shows the spatial distribution of fecal coliform for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). There is no Egyptian standard for fecal coliform; the used objective was previously used by (Heikal et al. 2007).

The average obtained values of the fecal coliform recorded 2250, 1500, 1075 and 15650 N\100 ml at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch in autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. Generally, the majority of records at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch ranged from 600 to 2000 cell /100ml, which are within the permissible limits (2000 N /100ml) during different seasons except the summer. The highest records of fecal coliform were recorded in summer, 30000 N /100 mL at the downstream of the industrial area (S5) and 27000 N /100mL at the upstream of the outlet of the Tala Drain (S1). Station No. 2 (S2), which represents the outlet of the Tala Drain, the fecal coliform recorded 2000, 1100, 20000 and 68000 N\100 mL in autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The highest records of fecal coliform were recorded in summer (68000 N /100 ml).

Figure (3-31): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of FC at the different sampling stations in the study area

The high values of fecal coliform along the Rosetta Branch may be attributed to the large amounts of untreated and partially treated domestic wastewater which receive from the Tala Drain. The high fecal coliform at S1 in summer is related to the same reason but due to other drains along the branch by to the Tala Drain. The fecal coliform concentration increases in the Tala Drain (S2) due to the increase in water temperature, decrease in water level and the discharge of domestic sewage and animal wastes into the drain. Untreated sewage, poorly maintained septic systems and farm animals which access to streams can cause high levels of fecal coliform bacteria to appear in a water body, as reported by (Ezzat et al. 2012). The boxplot of FC showed that there are four samples that the pH values were out of the trend of other samples three in the summer and one in the spring.

Total Algae

Figure (3-32) shows the spatial distribution of total Algae for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). The average obtained values of the fecal coliform recorded 3060, 3520, 1400 and 715 N/mL at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch in autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The highest records of total algae were recorded in winter, 5000 N/100 mL at the outlet of the industrial area (S8) and 4800 N /100mL at the downstream of it (S5). The values of total algae fluctuated from 180 to 1900 N/mL at the Tala drain outlet (S2) during summer and autumn, respectively.

The high total algae level may be attributed to the release of domestic waste water, agricultural runoff water and industrial effluents which lead to promote excessive growth of algae in water bodies, which results in their

eutrophication. The eutrophication will be the major problem of water due to excess nitrogen content in water, as reported by (Saad et al. 2011).

The Tala drain plays a significant role in change the water quality of the Rosetta Branch. It returns irrigation water into the branch which contains high concentration TDS, NO_3 and PO_4 . This will led to an increase in the salinity and cause a massive increase in the growth of algae in the Rosetta Branch as reported by (El-Sayed 2011).

Figure (3-32): Seasonal records and the boxplot representation of total algae at the different sampling stations in the study area

Generally, the majority of records for most parameters, such as: water temperature, turbidity, salinity, conductivity, SO_4 , NO_2 , NO_3 , chloride, Fe and Mn, were within the permissible limits, therefore they don't represent a risk to the environmental. The high recorded concentrations of COD, BOD, pH, TDS, PO_4 , fecal coliform and total algae and the low recorded concentrations in DO are causing serious ecological problems along the Rosetta Branch.

According to the previously mentioned data from physical, chemical and biological analyses, it is clear that the Tala Drain outlet station (S2), is seasonally suffering from chemical and biological pollution with varying

levels and varying nature which is probably due to the combination of several factors including industrial, agricultural and domestic waste discharge.

For Station No. 1 (S1), which is representing the sampling station directly located before the Tala Drain outlet, has high concentrations of the studied parameters. This is might be attributed to the other drains along the Rosetta Branch, particularly the El-Rahawy Drain, which have serious impacts on the water quality of the Rosetta Branch due to its high organic loads. Which affect suitability of the branch as a source of drinking water supply, as reported by (El Gammal and El Shazely 2008).

The present findings are in harmony with those reported by several authors who reported that the highest levels of pollution detected in Rosetta branch are always found at downstream drains sites and industrial companies at Kafr El-Zayat city (Abdo 2013; Alawy et al. 2015; Daifullah et al. 2003; Donia 2005; El-Amier et al. 2015; Ezzat et al. 2012; Mashali et al. 2009).

The gradual decrease in pollution levels along the Rosetta Branch (from downstream Tala Drain to downstream industrial companies at Kafr El-Zayat) could be interpreted in terms of “self-purification” phenomenon of streams and dilution effect concept concluded by (Ezzat et al. 2012).

It is worth to mention that, the worst water quality conditions were recorded during summer and autumn seasons. During the summer, the high rise in water temperature leads to an increased rate of water evaporation and thus, to an increase in pollution levels. During the autumn, the water level decreases, leading to an increase in pollutants load and a decrease in dilution effects, also accumulation of wastes in Tala drain which is usually accompanied by lowers water levels in the Rosetta Branch.

A set of box plots were applied for 18 parameters from 32 water samples collected along the Rosetta Branch and outlet of the Tala Drain by field

equipment and laboratory analysis. The data collected from short distance are all in close proximity to one another. Consequently, all collected data comes from a normal distribution, with the exception of pH, TDS, salinity, conductivity, NO₂ and fecal coliform featured some anomalous values.

3.3.2 Ecological Analysis

Dissolved oxygen is essential for aquatic life specially fish and other aquatic species. DO is considered as an important parameter in assessment of the degree of pollution in natural water (Mahmoud et al. 2008). It is controlled to susceptibility of fish to toxicity by chemicals which increase at low oxygen concentration (Erez et al. 1990). It allows to the aerobic bacteria to degrade a wide variety of organic matter and oxidize inorganic salts. The reduction of DO concentrations are result of biological respiration that are related to decomposition processes. In severe cases of reduced oxygen concentrations (whether natural or man-made), anaerobic conditions can occur (0 mg/l of oxygen), mainly close to the sediment-water interface as a result of decaying material. Concentrations below 5 mg/L may adversely affect the functioning and survival of biological communities and below 2 mg/L may lead to the death of most fish (Chapman 1996).

The field records of this study confirm the phenomenon of the death of fish (Fish kill) in the branch during summer due to the oxygen depletion. The average value of the dissolved oxygen (DO) at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch in summer were less than 2 mg/l, the lowest value was about 1.07 mg/l at S6, as can be seen in Figure (3-33). Fish can't survive when DO record drops less than 2 mg/l, as reported by (Chapman 1996).

This could be attributed to the increase of water temperature and the drainage water from Tala drain which characterized by high load of organic wastes

and the microbial activity that degraded the organic matter led to the oxygen consumption. Moreover, the depletion of DO may return to the exhaustion of dissolved oxygen by oxidation of huge organic matter, which is discharged into the Rosetta Branch through the wastewater of different companies at Kafr El-Zayat city, as reported by (El Gohary 2015).

Figure (3-33): Records of DO during 2014-2015 at the different sampling stations in the study area

The results of water samples recorded high water temperature, high concentrations of nutrients (such as NO_3) and fecal coliform, particularly in the summer, as shown in Figures (3-33) - (3-35), respectively.

The solubility of oxygen decreases as temperature increase. Generally it can be noticed that the increase of water temperature significantly affect the dissolved oxygen during the summer at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch and in outlet of the Tala Drain (32.8°C), as shown in Figure (3-34).

Figure (3-34): Records of water temperature during 2014-2015 at the different sampling stations in the study area

Also, the highest average value of Nitrate (NO_3) was recorded at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch during summer (0.57 mg/l) as shown in Figure (3-35). Higher concentration of nitrate in water of the Rosetta branch can create a large oxygen demand and cause algae to grow in large quantity. Dead algae can cause oxygen depletion problems which in turn can kill fishes and other aquatic organisms.

Figure (3-35): Records of NO_3 during 2014-2015 at the different sampling stations in the study area

The results of this study recorded higher rates of fecal coliform contamination in summer, to be about 68000 cell /100ml at the Tala Drain (station No. 2) and 30000 cell /100ml at the downstream station of the industrial area at Kafr El-Zayat city (station No. 5) during summer, as shown in Figure (3-36). These values are much higher than the permissible limit. The fecal coliform concentration increases in the Tala Drain (S2) due to the increase in water temperature, decrease in water level and the discharge of domestic sewage and animal wastes into the drain. Untreated sewage, poorly maintained septic systems and farm animals which access to streams can cause high levels of fecal coliform bacteria to appear in a water body. The increase in fecal coliform concentration leads to increase in turbidity levels and to a decrease in dissolved oxygen concentration. Higher turbidity decreases the rate of photosynthesis because the suspended particles absorb more heat and reduce the amount of sunlight penetrating the water, which, leads to a decrease in DO production. The severe reduction in dissolved oxygen concentrations leads to fish kill during summer.

Figure (3-36): Records of FC during 2014-2015 at the different sampling stations in the study area

Chapter (4)

WATER QUALITY ASSESSMENT

This chapter presents the application of two assessment approaches, Water Quality Index (WQI) approach and the statistical analysis approach, to the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city.

Water Quality Index (WQI) is considered as one of the most effective approaches for water quality assessment. WQI is a mathematical tool used to integrate complex records to generate a single score that evaluates the overall status of water quality to the public as well as decision and policy makers. It is based on group of records including; physical, chemical and biological parameters of the water body using specific methods (Simoes et al. 2008).

Also, Statistical analysis is considered as one of the most effective approaches for water quality assessment. The application of different statistical analysis approaches, such as correlation matrix, principal component analysis (PCA) and factor analysis (FA) help identify important components or factors accounting for most of the variances for any river system. Statistical analyses are applied to reduce the number of variables to a small number of indices while attempting to preserve the present relationships between parameters in the original water quality data (Shrestha and Kazama 2007).

4.1 WQI of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat City

Two of the best known water quality indices, which have been frequently used, have been developed to estimate the overall water quality status of the

Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the period from November 2014 to August 2015. These water quality indices are the National Sanitation Foundation Water Quality Index (NSFWQI) and the Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment Water Quality Index (CCMEWQI) (previously described in the second chapter). The water quality records were seasonally collected and analyzed from seven sampling stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city and from one station at the Tala Drain outlet, as explained in detail in the previous chapters, Figure (4-1).

Figure (4-1): Schematic diagram for location of the stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

4.1.1 NSFQI

Based on the available measured water quality parameters of the Rosetta Branch, eight parameters were used to apply NSFQI, total suspended solids records weren't available for all stations because of the recording equipment to measure this parameter wasn't available in the field. The used parameters are: dissolved oxygen (% sat), fecal coliform (N/100 ml), pH (standard unit), temperature change (degrees C), total phosphate (mg/l), nitrate (mg/), turbidity (NTU) and biochemical oxygen demand (mg/l). These parameters were available for stations (S1, S2, S4, S5 and S8). While for stations S3, S6 and S7, NSFQI was calculated based on six parameters, biochemical oxygen demand, fecal coliform and total solids weren't available.

NSFWQI can be calculated as follows (Abbasi 2012):

$$\text{NSFWQI} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i \times Q_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i} \quad (4-1)$$

Where: W_i : weight factor of the i^{th} parameter (Appendix A).

Q_i : sub-index quality value i^{th} parameter, can be obtained from the appropriate sub-index rating graph (Appendix A).

For temperature change, S1 was considered as the reference station due to the missing historical records for the considered sampling stations.

An expression for the dissolved oxygen saturation concentration (DO_{sat}) at the sea level for freshwater as a function of water temperature, which is given in (APHA 2005), Equation (4-2), was used to calculate DO (%sat) at the different sampling stations, Equation (4-3). The used expression is as follows:

$$\ln DO_{sat} = -139.34411 + \frac{1.575701 * 10^5}{T_w} - \frac{6.642308 * 10^7}{T_w^2} + \frac{1.243800 * 10^{10}}{T_w^3} - \frac{8.621949 * 10^{11}}{T_w^4} \quad (4-2)$$

$$DO (\% \text{ sat}) = \left(\frac{DO_i}{DO_{sat}} \right) \% \quad (4-3)$$

Where:

DO_{sat} : Freshwater DO saturation concentration in mg/L at the sea level

T_w : Water temperature in (°K) ([°K] = [°C] + 273.150)

DO_i : Measured DO concentration at the sampling station Si

Figure (5-2) shows the spatial distribution of NSFQI for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). It can be noticed that the average value of NSFQI recorded 61, 68, 66 and 55 at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch in autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The water quality status of the study area in winter and spring is similar, which is classified as “Medium”. The worst water quality status of the study area is in the summer, which is classified as “Medium”. This decrease in the water quality is due to the increase of fecal coliform concentration and the decrease of DO concentration. Check the previous chapter.

Figure (4-2): NSF WQI along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during 2014-2015

Station No. 2 (S2) represents the Tala Drain, which receives discharge from dairy industry and agricultural drainage, as well as untreated domestic wastewater. This station gives the lowest NSF WQI in the summer (41) which is considered “Bad”, due to the relatively high concentrations of BOD, PO_4 , fecal coliform and the increase in water temperature, which inversely affects DO. Check the previous chapter.

Station No. 5 (S5) represents the downstream of the industrial area of Kafr El-Zayat city, which is considered the critical station of the study area due to the industrial pollution. NSF WQI values for S5 ranges from 48 to 51 in autumn and summer, respectively, the water quality status is rated as “Bad” to “Medium”. This is may be attributed to the relatively high concentrations of BOD and fecal coliform and low concentrations of DO. GIS technique was

developed to present NSFQI, which help in water quality management along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city.

The spatial distribution of NSFQI values in summer at different stations, using GIS technique, can be seen in Figure (4-3).

Figure (4-3): NSFQI along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during summer 2015 using GIS

4.1.2 CCMEWQI

Based on the available measured water quality parameters of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city, eleven physical, chemical and biological parameters were used to calculate CCMEWQI. These parameters are: dissolved oxygen (mg/l), total dissolved solids (mg/l), nitrate (mg/l), sulfate (mg/l), iron (mg/l), manganese (mg/l), fecal coliform (N/100 ml), pH (standard unit), water temperature (degrees C), chemical oxygen demand

(mg/l) and biochemical oxygen demand (mg/l). COD, BOD and fecal coliform records weren't available at stations S3, S6 and S7, which were assigned as minor stations.

CCMEWQI can be calculated according to the following equation (CCME 2001):

$$\text{CCMEWQI} = 100 - \sqrt{\frac{F_1^2 + F_2^2 + F_3^2}{1.732}} \quad (2-5)$$

Where: F_1 represents scope: The percentage of variables above the standards.

F_2 represents frequency: The frequency by which the objectives are not met.

F_3 represents amplitude: The range to which the failed tests are above the standards.

The constant, 1.732, is a scaling factor (square root of three) to ensure the index varies between 0 and 100.

The factors equations, method of calculations and categories are presented in Appendix (A). The Egyptian water quality standards for fresh waterways, decree No. 49 – Law 48/1982 – Article No. 60 amended in 2013, were used as objectives for this study, as shown in the previous chapter, Table (3-3). For fecal coliform, as there is no Egyptian standard for it, the used objective was previously used by (Heikal et al. 2007).

Figure (4-4) shows the spatial distribution of CCME WQI for the Rosetta Branch and the Tala Drain at Kafr El-Zayat city for the studied period (from November 2014 to August 2015). It can be noticed that the water quality status of the study area is better in autumn, winter and spring, as the averages of CCMEWQI are 81, 89 and 89, respectively, which are considered as “Good” at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch. The worst water quality status of the study area is in the summer, the average CCME WQI is

63, which is classified as “Marginal”. CCMEWQI for Station No.5 is 51 in summer. This decrease in the water quality returns to the increase of water temperature, DO and fecal coliform concentrations.

Figure (4-4): CCMEWQI along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during 2014-2015

Similar to NSFQI, Station No.2 gives the lowest CCME WQI values, range from 37 to 58 in summer and spring, respectively. The water quality status is rated as “Poor” to “Marginal”, according to CCMEWQI categories. This decrease in the water quality returns to the increase of BOD, COD during the spring and the increase of fecal coliform and DO concentration during the summer. Check the previous chapter.

GIS technique was developed to present CCMEWQI, which help in water quality management along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. The spatial distribution of CCMEWQI values in summer at different stations, using GIS technique, can be seen in Figure (4-5).

Figure (4-5): CCMEWQI along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during summer 2015 using GIS

4.2 Water Quality Statistical Analysis of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat City

Correlation Analysis, Factor Analysis (FA) and Principle Component Analysis (PCA) were applied for the assessment of spatial and temporal variations of a measured water quality data set of field records, which have been collected from the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city, during the period from November 2014 to August 2015 at 5 major stations (S1, S2, S4, S5 and S8). For calculating the statistical analysis, a total of 18 parameters were considered. These parameters are: dissolved oxygen (mg/l), total

dissolved solids (mg/l), salinity (ppt), conductivity (μs), nitrate (mg/l), nitrite (mg/l), sulfate (mg/l), phosphate (mg/l), iron (mg/l), manganese (mg/l), Chloride (mg/l), fecal coliform (N/100 ml), total algae (N/ml), pH, water temperature (degrees C), turbidity (NTU), chemical oxygen demand (mg/l) and biochemical oxygen demand (mg/l).

All mathematical and statistical computations were carried out using Microsoft Office Excel 2010 and IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 software.

4.2.1 Correlation Analysis

The correlation matrix was prepared within the analyzed parameters at 8 stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. The nature of correlations among the different parameters is provided in Table (4-2).

It is observed that negative correlations were found to exist between pH values and all studied parameters for all seasons, except DO, COD, Fe and chloride. Positive correlations were obtained between water temperature values and all selected parameters for all seasons, except DO, salinity, TDS, PO_4 , Mn and total algae. Negative correlations were found between DO values and all studied parameters for all seasons, except BOD, NO_3 , Fe, Mn and fecal coliform; this finding indicates the important role of DO in improving water quality.

Analytical results also showed parameters such as salinity and conductivity exhibit very strong correlation with TDS ($r = 1$ and 0.96), respectively. TDS has a strong positive correlation with a number of variables like salinity, conductivity, nitrate, nitrite, sulfate and phosphate. Thus, TDS is the single variable that gives a reasonably good indication of a number of related variables.

Strong positive correlation was obtained between NO_2 and NO_3 ($r = 0.68$) during all seasons. NO_2 and NO_3 were significant correlation which means that NO_2 and NO_3 are dependent on each other, when nitrite decreases leading to nitrate increase due to the oxidation of NO_2 into NO_3 . In addition, moderate positive correlation between NO_3 and PO_4 . It is worth to mention that, there is a significant negative relationship between different fecal coliform and DO ($r = -0.5$). This finding indicates the important role of DO in improving water quality and illustrated the extent of the link between DO depletion and the strong evidence for bacterial water deterioration, as reported by (Korium and Toufeek 2008). DO showed negative correlations with studied trace metals (Fe and Mn), which indicate the important role of dissolved oxygen in precipitation of metals as metal oxides and hydroxides, as reported by (El-Bouraie et al. 2010). pH showed a negative correlation with most studied parameter, except dissolved oxygen ($r = 0.50$). Fecal coliform concentrations are positively correlated with discharge and water temperature and generally are negatively correlated with pH and DO and this is in agreement with (Shehata and Badr 2010). The positive correlation between Fe and Mn ($r = 0.42$) indicated that the association of two elements originates from a common source during transportation and depositional reactions, as reported by (Abdel-Satar and Elewa 2001). When parameters exhibit strong or moderate correlation with each other, Water Quality Index (WQI) may not characterize the quality of water. Therefore, it is important to convert correlated parameters into uncorrelated parameters for efficient forecasting of water quality. Principal component analysis (PCA) provides a suitable method to transform correlated parameters into uncorrelated components.

Table (4-1): Correlation matrix for the analyzed parameters along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during 2014-2015

4.2.2 Factor analysis (FA)/Principal component analysis (PCA)

The principal component analyses for the water quality records of Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city are shown in Table (4-2). It includes loadings for the rotated component matrix, eigenvalues for each component, percent and cumulative percent of variance explained by each component.

Table (4-2): Factor loading matrix and total variance explained for the analyzed parameters along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during 2014-2015

Parameters	Principal component				
	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	F ₅
Water Temp.	-0.012	0.894 [*]	0.043	0.208	0.045
TDS	0.962 [*]	-0.181	0.048	-0.136	0.077
Turbidity	-0.068	0.714 ^{**}	0.422	-0.015	0.122
pH	-0.186	0.036	0.664 ^{**}	0.214	0.528 ^{**}
DO	0.056	-0.615	0.592 ^{**}	0.042	0.379
Salinity	0.961 [*]	-0.171	0.063	-0.136	0.071
Conductivity	0.976 [*]	0.043	0.057	-0.056	0.086
BOD	0.535 ^{**}	-0.057	-0.381	0.614 ^{**}	-0.125
COD	-0.092	0.014	0.382	0.717 ^{**}	-0.329
NO₂	0.832 [*]	0.004	0.066	0.346	0.078
NO₃	0.749 ^{**}	0.353	0.101	-0.026	-0.326
PO₄	0.745 ^{**}	-0.549	-0.189	-0.026	0.191
SO₄	0.884 [*]	0.139	0.063	-0.282	0.144
Fe	-0.157	0.293	-0.374	0.387	0.623 ^{**}
Mn	-0.100	-0.212	-0.652 ^{**}	0.449	0.301
Chloride	0.520 ^{**}	-0.011	0.274	0.571 ^{**}	-0.289
Fecal Coliform	0.400	0.652 ^{**}	-0.311	-0.263	0.022
Total Algae	-0.312	-0.695 ^{**}	-0.027	-0.020	-0.244
Eigenvalue	6.081	3.156	1.962	1.922	1.815
Variance (%)	33.783	17.535	10.898	10.678	10.086
Cumulative (%)	33.783	51.317	62.215	72.894	82.979

* Variables that have loadings >0.75 ** Variables that have loadings (0.75–0.5)

The factor analysis generated five significant factors which explain 82.979% of the variation in the data set. It indicates that the principal components from the first to the fifth are (in order): 33.783%, 17.535%, 10.898%, 10.678% and 10.086% of the total variance. The number of principal components justified in this study can be judged from the shown scree plot in Figure (4-6). The eigenvalues of the first five principal components are greater than 1, which can be used to assess the dominant hydro geochemical processes.

The first factor (F_1) has strong positive loadings on TDS, salinity, conductivity, NO_2 and SO_4 , while it has moderate positive loadings on BOD, NO_3 , PO_4 and Chloride. This factor represents the agricultural drainage and nutrient effluent problem. This may be interpreted as the municipal sewage runoff.

Second factor (F_2) represents the seasonal effect of temperature and the biological pollution. It shows moderate positive loadings on turbidity and fecal coliform and moderate negative loadings on total algae, while water temperature has strong positive loadings (0.894). This can be interpreted as anthropogenic contributions. Due to a lot of dissolved nutrient coupled with the higher temperature, may lead to increased algae activity. Then, the inverse relationship between the total algae indicator and turbidity can be explained.

For the third principal component (F_3), the concentrations of pH and DO show moderate positive loadings and the concentration of Mn shows moderate negative loadings. F_3 represents the point sources pollution. Mn presence is an indication of the parent rock influence. F_3 represents the industrial pollution.

Fourth factor (F_4) has moderate positive loadings on BOD and COD; it represents the municipal and industrial pollution. This may be interpreted as

seasonal effects and biochemical pollution, such as eutrophication from human activities and domestic wastewater. BOD is a controlling factor; factor 4 has the moderator positive loadings than the factor 1.

Fifth factor (F_5) has moderate positive loadings on pH and Fe. Although pH is a controlling factor, factor 3 has the moderator positive loadings than the factor 5. Fe extracted from the parent rock of the area is the significance in this factor. F_5 represents the industrial pollution.

Figure (4-6): The Scree plot of the principal components for the analyzed parameters along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during 2014-2015

4.3 Summing Up

Table (4-3) summarizes the results of the application of two water quality indices along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during 2014-2015, based on the measured water quality parameters at 8 stations.

Table (4-3): A summary of WQI results along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during 2014-2015

Water quality Indices (WQIs)								
At the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch								
WQI	CCME				NSF			
Season	Autumn	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Spring	Summer
Score	81	89	89	63	61	68	66	55
Status	Good			Marginal	Medium			
At outlet of the Tala Drain (Station No.2)								
WQI	CCME				NSF			
Season	Autumn	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Spring	Summer
Score	85	84	69	37	63	60	59	41
Status	Good		Fair	Marginal	Medium			Bad

The results of WQIs showed that DO and fecal coliform are the main cause of the value of water quality reduction at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch particularly during the summer.

A comparison of two these water quality indices is also performed under the study considering their merits and demerits. Table (4-4) explains about the advantages and disadvantages of selected WQI methods.

Table (4-5) summarizes the results of the application of two statistical analysis approaches along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during 2014-2015, based on the measured water quality parameters at 8 stations.

Table (4-4): A comparison of the advantages and disadvantages of selected WQI methods

Water quality Indices (WQIs)	
CCMEWQI	NSFWQI
Advantages	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexibility in the selection of input parameters and objectives. - Adaptability to different legal requirements and different water uses. - Suitable tool for water quality evaluation in a specific location. - Tolerance to missing data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Summarizes data in a single index value in an objective, rapid and reproducible manner. - Evaluation between areas and identifying changes in water quality. - Index value relate to a potential water use.
Disadvantages	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of portability of the index to different ecosystem types. - The same importance is given to all variables. - No combination with other indicators or biological data - F1 not working appropriately when too few variables are considered or when too much covariance exists among them. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Represents general water quality, it does not represent specific use of the water. - Loss of data during data handling. - Lack of dealing with uncertainty and subjectivity present in complex environmental issues.

Table (4-5): A summary of statistical analysis results along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during 2014-2015

Statistical Analysis Approaches							
Correlation Analysis		Factor Analysis (FA) /Principle Component Analysis (PCA)					
r	Parameters		F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	F ₅
Very Strong	TDS & Salinity	Strong positive loadings	TDS	Water temp.	-	-	-
	TDS & Conductivity		Salinity				
Salinity & PO ₄	Conductivity						
Salinity & SO ₄	NO ₂ SO ₄						
Strong	NO ₂ & NO ₃ SO ₄ & NO ₂ , NO ₃						
Moderate	Fecal coliform & DO, Water temp., Total algae Water Temp. & DO NO ₃ & PO ₄ BOD & NO ₂ , PO ₄	Moderate positive loadings	NO ₃ PO ₄ Chloride	Turbidity Fecal coliform Total algae	pH DO Mn	BOD COD	Fe
		Factor representation	Agricultural drainage and nutrient effluent	Municipal and Biological pollution	Industrial pollution	Municipal and industrial pollution	Industrial pollution

Chapter (5)

NUMERICAL MODELING & ANALYSIS

This chapter presents the developing and calibration of the hydrodynamic and water quality model for the selected study area, the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. Moreover, based on the developed model, application of the suggested water quality management scenarios to enhance the water quality status of the study area is discussed.

5.1 Model Development

MIKE 11 modeling system was selected for developing a hydrodynamic and water quality model for the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city in the present study. MIKE 11 is a fully dynamic, one-dimensional modeling tool, it includes different modules for run-off simulations, hydrodynamics, flood forecasting, transport and dilution of dissolved substances, sediment transport, and river morphology as well as various water quality processes (DHI 2012). The Hydrodynamic module (HD), Advection-Dispersion module (AD) and Ecological Laboratory module (ECO Lab) were selected for current case study.

The input data for the model are:

1. The bathymetry of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city.
2. The stream flow and water quality records of the Rosetta Branch (start and end sections), the Tala drain and the industrial companies' outlets all times during the simulation period (as boundary conditions).

3. The Rosetta Branch water levels, discharge and water quality records at the beginning of the simulation (as initial conditions).

The limitation of available data for the study area, in particular the hydrological data, is considered as the main constraint of this work. This problem made the developing of a hydrodynamic and water quality model for the Rosetta Branch is a challenge. The simulation period was selected to be from November 2014 to August 2015, according to the designed monitoring program.

5.1.1 Bathymetry

River bathymetry (topography) is the term used for the finite difference representation of the water body. The Rosetta Branch bathymetry is based on the topography of 24 cross sections, according to field survey, are presented in Appendix (B). The branch bathymetry was developed using two editors; the network editor and the cross section editor, as following:

5.1.1.1 River Network

The network editor is used for editing and viewing network data. This editor gives an overview of the current setup and provides a common link to the other editors of MIKE 11. The MIKE 11 model provides a graphical user interface and requires a river network to be drawn on a grid (mesh) of cells that represent geographical area to a referenced scale and coordinates. Furthermore, cross sections can also be edited using the river cross section editor, which is accessible from this editor. The network editor has two main functions: River network input and editing, and overview of all model information in the current simulation.

The entire network of Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city was developed based on the selected 24 point's coordinates (Longitude and Latitude), which were estimated using a GPS equipment (Garmin GPSMAP 78s). All the branch alignments were digitized according to its chain-age (the point location along the river) and based on a reference scaled map in the background of the editor screen. Figure (5-1) shows the developed branch network.

Figure (5-1): The developed Rosetta Branch network at Kafr El-Zayat city

5.1.1.2 Cross Sections

The cross section editor manages, stores and displays all the model cross section information. In MIKE 11 there are two types of cross section data; the raw survey data and the derived processed data. The raw data describes the

shape of the cross section and typically comes from a section survey of the river. The processed data is derived from the raw data and contains all information used by the computer model (e.g., water level, cross section area, flow width, hydraulic/resistance radius). The processed data could be calculated by the cross section editor or entered manually. In this research work, the processed data is calculated by the cross section editor. The raw data of the derived cross-sections is obtained from the field-survey along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr EL-Zayat city. The derived model cross-sections are presented in Appendix (B). Figure (5-2) shows the cross-section setting and an example for one of the derived cross-sections for the study area.

Figure (5-2): The cross-section setting along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

The cross-section file contains stream bed cross-sections at specific locations along the river network as shown in Figure (5-3).

Figure (5-3): River network with locations of the cross sections along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

5.1.2 Boundary Conditions

The boundary editor is the most important part of the modeling system. It is used to specify boundary conditions of MIKE11 model. It is used not only to specify common boundary conditions such as water levels and inflow hydrographs but also for the specification of lateral flows along the river reaches, solute concentrations of the inflow hydrographs, various meteorological data and certain boundary conditions used in connection with structures applied in MIKE 11 model. The boundary file consists of boundary conditions in a time series format for the river network's boundaries. The water level boundary must be applied to either the upstream or downstream boundary condition in the model. The data of water quality values, water temperature and water level in the upstream, downstream and points of

sources in a separate file enters to the model as the boundary conditions. Hydrodynamic and water quality records for the simulation period (starting from November 2014 to August 2015) at different stations were used to provide the boundary conditions for the proposed model. Hydrodynamic and water quality parameters must be identified for all boundaries, upstream section (BC 1) and downstream section (BC 2) of the study area. Tala drain (BC 3) and the industrial companies (BC 4) outlets are expressed as point sources, as shown in Figure (5-4).

Figure (5-4): Schematic diagram for the locations of the boundary conditions of the proposed Rosetta Branch model.

The considered boundary conditions include: water levels, water temperature, salinity, and water quality records of the Rosetta Branch and the discharge of the Tala drain and the industrial companies at Kafr El-Zayat city.

Typical daily water levels for the Rosetta Branch at at Kafr El-Zayat city are used as water level boundary conditions for the upstream and downstream sections of the study area, Figure (5-5). These field records were recorded by the Egyptian Ministry of Water Resources and Irrigation (MWRI 2015).

For the field water quality records at the boundary condition stations, Figures (5-6) to (5-10) show water temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and fecal coliform (FC) profiles during the simulation period, according to the designed monitoring program.

Figure (5-5): Typical water levels profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-6): Water temperature profiles of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the simulation period

Figure (5-7): Salinity profiles of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the simulation period

Figure (5-8): Dissolved oxygen profiles of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the simulation period

Figure (5-9): Biochemical oxygen demand profiles of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the simulation period

Figure (5-10): Fecal coliform profiles of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the simulation period

5.1.3 Initial Conditions

To start the model computations, initial values for all state variables must be provided only at the beginning time of simulation. The initial conditions were assigned for the upstream and downstream sections of the study area, S1 and S5, respectively. The model interpolates these conditions to cover the whole study area. The proposed initial conditions for the model are shown in table (5-1).

Table (5-1): The proposed initial conditions of the Rosetta Branch model

The module	State variable	Station	Value	Comment
Hydro-dynamic	Water level	Upstream (S1)	2.85 m	-
		Downstream (S5)	2.85 m	-
Advection-Dispersion	Water temperature	Upstream (S1)	21.7 °C	-
		Downstream (S5)	21.7 °C	-
	Salinity	Upstream (S1)	0.38 ppt	-
		Downstream (S5)	0.38 ppt	-
Water Quality (ECO Lab)	Dissolved oxygen	Upstream (S1)	12.3 mg/l	In range
		Downstream (S5)	3.12 mg/l	Out of range
	Biochemical oxygen demand	Upstream (S1)	11 mg/l	Out of range
		Downstream (S5)	16 mg/l	
	Fecal coliform	Upstream (S1)	6000 N/100mL	Out of range
		Downstream (S5)	1000 N/100mL	In range

5.1.4 Model Calibration

In this study, the proposed model is simulated for the different four seasons, November 2014 - August 2015. The proposed model was calibrated using default and non-default processes coefficients, which were determined

according to the characteristics of the study area. Table (5-2) presents the non-default calibrated coefficients.

Table (5-2): List of non-default calibration coefficients for the Rosetta Branch model

The Module	Coefficient	Value
Hydrodynamic	Chezy number	50 m ^{1/2} /s
	Wind friction factor	0.001
	Time step interval	20 sec
Advection-Dispersion	Dispersion factor	10 m ² /s
	Temperature: Latitude	33 Degrees
	Temperature: Maximum absorbed solar radiation	6000 per day
	Temperature: Emitted heat radiation	2000 per day
ECO Lab	Oxygen Processes: No. of reaeration expression	5
	Oxygen Processes: Max. oxygen production by photosynthesis	3/d
	Oxygen Processes: Production/respiration	2
	Oxygen Processes: Reaeration constant	5 /d
	Coliforms: 1st Order decay Fecal coliforms	0.1/d
	Coliforms: Arrhenius temperature coefficient	0.9
	Coliforms: Light coefficient of decay rate	10
	Coliforms: Light Extinction Coefficient	8/m

Calibration process based on the fixation of all coefficients except the tested one, such as Chezy coefficient. For example, the Chezy coefficient was tested for the range from 30 m^{1/2} /s to 50 m^{1/2} /s, the latter value gives a good agreement for the compared measured and simulated values. As Chezy

coefficient indicates the bed roughness, it is logical for the bed of Rosetta Branch to be more rough due to its nature as a natural water body and due to the different discharged wastes. This procedure of calibration process has been applied for all model calibration coefficients. For the other model coefficients not measured in this study, default values provided by the code software were used as recommended by MIKE 11 modeling manual (DHI 2012).

5.1.5 Model Evaluation

The hydrodynamic, advection dispersion and water quality modules of MIKE 11 model were calibrated by comparing simulated results to the measured values at different monitoring stations along the Rosetta Branch. Two statistical measures were applied to these results to quantify the accuracy of model and to estimate the errors in the simulated results. These statistical measures are the Absolute Mean Error (AME) and the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). AME and RMSE are considered as the most frequently used Error-statistics. The AME indicates how far, on the average, simulated values are from measured values, while the RMSE indicates the spread of how far the computed values deviate from the observed data. AME and RMSE are computed according to the following equations:

Absolute Mean Error (AME)

$$AME = \frac{\sum |\text{Observed value} - \text{Simulated value}|}{\text{Number of Observations}} \quad (5-1)$$

Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (\text{Observed value} - \text{Simulated value})^2}{\text{Number of Observations}}} \quad (5-2)$$

5.2 Analysis of Results & Discussions

The proposed hydrodynamic and ecological model of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city has been calibrated for a simulation period from November 2014 to August 2015. The developed Rosetta Branch model consists of three modules; the hydrodynamic module (HD), the advection-dispersion module (AD) and the water quality module (ECO Lab). Six indicated hydrodynamic and water quality parameters were chosen to present the calibration results; these parameters are water levels, water temperature, salinity, DO, BOD and FC.

5.2.1 The Hydrodynamic Model (HD)

The hydrodynamic model of the Rosetta Branch simulates the hydraulic properties of the model, which include the water levels, discharges and velocities. The cross-section properties and the acting weather conditions are considered. The water levels have been chosen to present the results due to the availability of measured records.

- The surface water levels

Figure (5-11) shows the measured and simulated longitudinal profiles of the surface water levels of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city (for all stations) during the studied calibration period. Applicable match between the simulated and measured trends of the water surface levels can be noticed. The AME and RMSE values, of the calibration process, shows a full agreement of the simulated water surface levels with the observed water surface levels. This full agreement returns to the short length of the studied area, about 3 km, which doesn't reveal any changes in the water levels.

Figure (5-11): The simulated and measured water levels during Nov. 2014 to Aug. 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city.

5.2.2 The Advection-Dispersion Model (AD)

The MIKE 11 advection-dispersion module of the Rosetta Branch model advances the hydrodynamic model by simulating the decays of determinants and the transport of solutes such as: transportation of conservative components (salinity) and thermal conditions (water temperature).

Two parameters have been chosen to present the results during the studied calibration period (November 2014 - August 2015). These parameters are: water temperature and salinity.

5.2.2.1 The water temperature

The measured and simulated water temperature profiles during four different seasons (2014-2015), at all monitoring stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city, can be seen in Figures (5-12) – (5-15). The AME are estimated by about 0, 0.11, 0.27 and 0.11°C, for autumn 2014, winter 2015, spring 2015 and summer 2015, respectively. While the corresponding RMSE are estimated by about 0, 0.12, 0.28 and 0.11°C, for autumn 2014, winter

2015, spring 2015 and summer 2015, respectively. The average AME and RMSE values for the studied stations are 0.12 °C and 0.13 °C, respectively. Although there are only six available limited records per season (6 records), the figures show similar trends for the measured records.

Figure (5-12): Measured and simulated water temperature profiles during autumn 2014 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-13): Measured and simulated water temperature profiles during winter 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-14): Measured and simulated water temperature profiles during spring 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-15): Measured and simulated water temperature profiles during summer 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

5.2.2.2 The Salinity

Salinity was chosen for calibration process because it is considered a conservative material and it is an excellent water mass tracer. Figures (5-16) – (5-19) show the measured and simulated seasonal profiles of salinity at the different monitoring stations, along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city, during the studied calibration period. The measured records are closely lies on the simulated trend in a very good way in all figures. The AME are estimated by about 0.03, 0.1, 0.02 and 0.01 ppt for autumn 2014, winter 2015, spring 2015 and summer 2015, respectively, while the corresponding RMSE are 0.04, 0.11, 0.02 and 0.02 ppt, respectively. The average AME and RMSE values for the studied stations are 0.04 and 0.05 ppt, respectively, which is considered as a very good indicator for the calibration process.

Figure (5-16): Measured and simulated salinity profiles during autumn 2014 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-17): Measured and simulated salinity profiles during winter 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-18): Measured and simulated salinity profiles during spring 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-19): Measured and simulated salinity profiles during summer 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

5.2.3 Water Quality Model (ECO Lab)

The MIKE 11 water quality module, which is an extension of the advection-dispersion module, is used to simulate the reaction processes of multi compound systems and a variety of biochemical interaction processes, including DO and BOD computations and simulations of nutrients,

macrophytes and plankton. The Ecolab module offers a number of standard templates, containing different combinations of water quality determinants and processes. The standard template, entitled ‘WQlevel4ColiPhos.Ecolab’, was selected and modified to suit the specific requirements of this study. Three parameters have been chosen to present the model results during the studied calibration period (November 2014 - August 2015). These parameters are: dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and fecal coliform (FC).

5.2.3.1 Dissolved oxygen (DO)

Figures (5-20) – (5-23) show the measured and simulated seasonal profiles of dissolved oxygen (DO) at all the different monitoring stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the studied calibration period (November 2014 - August 2015). The figures reveal a good matching between the measured and the simulated records. The AME are estimated by about 0.6, 0.58, 0.59 and 0.86 mg/l for autumn 2014, winter 2015, spring 2015 and summer 2015, respectively, while the corresponding RMSE are 0.83, 0.75, 0.68 and 0.87 mg/l, respectively. The average AME and RMSE values for the studied stations are 0.65 and 0.78 mg/l, respectively.

Figure (5-20): Measured and simulated dissolved oxygen profiles during autumn 2014 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-21): Measured and simulated dissolved oxygen profiles during winter 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-22): Measured and simulated dissolved oxygen profiles during spring 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-23): Measured and simulated dissolved oxygen concentration profiles summer 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

5.2.3.2 Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD)

Figures (5-24) – (5-27) show the measured and simulated seasonal profiles of biochemical oxygen demand at all the different monitoring stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the studied calibration period. Unfortunately, according to the monitoring program, measured BOD records are available at only three control stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. Such limited measured records can negatively affect the

calibration process results. The AME are estimated by about 0.47, 1.13, 0.8 and 0.25 mg/l for autumn 2014, winter 2015, spring 2015 and summer 2015, respectively, while the corresponding RMSE are 0.81, 1.31, 1.06 and 0.54 mg/l, respectively. The average AME and RMSE values for the studied stations are 0.65 and 0.78 mg/l, respectively. The figures show a good matching between the measured and the simulated records.

Figure (5-24): Measured and simulated biochemical oxygen demand profiles during autumn 2014 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-25): Measured and simulated biochemical oxygen demand profiles during winter 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-26): Measured and simulated biochemical oxygen demand profiles during spring 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-27): Measured and simulated biochemical oxygen demand profiles during summer 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

5.2.3.3 Fecal coliform (FC)

Figures (5-28) – (5-31) show the measured and simulated seasonal profiles of fecal coliform at all the different monitoring stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the studied calibration period. Unfortunately, according to the monitoring program, measured FC records are available at only three control stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. Such limited measured records can negatively affect the calibration process results. The AME are estimated by about 102, 42, 60 and 1076 N/100 mL for autumn 2014, winter 2015, spring 2015 and summer 2015, respectively, while the corresponding RMSE are 250, 61, 87 and 2041 N/100 mL. The average AME and RMSE values for the studied stations are 320 and 609 N/100 mL, respectively. The figures show a good matching between the measured and the simulated records.

Figure (5-28): Measured and simulated fecal coliform profiles during autumn 2014 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-29): Measured and simulated fecal coliform profiles during winter 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-30): Measured and simulated fecal coliform profiles during spring 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Figure (5-31): Measured and simulated fecal coliform profiles during summer 2015 along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city.

5.3 Water Quality Mitigation Scenarios

The developed model has been used to investigate some feasible scenarios for the water quality status of the Rosetta Branch, to obtain a better ecosystem for the branch. Water quality mitigation scenarios are simulated using

the collected water quality records and the pre-calibrated Rosetta Branch model as a base condition. It should be declared that to investigate the effect of a suggested scenario on the water quality parameters, other initial and boundary conditions are considered as the same as the calibration conditions. The main objective of this investigation is to propose alternative solutions to improve the water quality status of the studied reach. Six water quality management scenarios, using MIKE 11 hydrodynamic (HD), advection-dispersion (AD), and water quality (ECO Lab) modules, are designated as explained in Figure (5-32).

Figure (5-32): The Rosetta Branch water quality management scenarios at Kafr El-Zayat city

These suggested scenarios may mitigate and enhance the deteriorated water quality status of the Rosetta Branch which threat drinking water and aquatic

life. The change of parameters reference concentrations is calculated during each season for each parameter using the following equation:

$$\Delta = \frac{\sum C_{sc} - C_{ref}}{\sum C_{ref}} \% \quad (5-3)$$

Where: Δ : % Change of reference value.

C_{sc} : Parameter value due to applied scenario.

C_{ref} : Parameter reference value.

The changes of parameters are assigned at each figure for each scenario.

5.3.1 Scenario No.1: Diverting of the Industrial Effluents to the City Sewer System

This scenario can be conducted through diverting the industrial effluents from the industrial companies at Kafr El-Zayat city to the city sewer system (as planned). The calibrated Rosetta Branch model was modified according to this scenario. The indicator parameters are salinity, dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and fecal coliform (FC). According to the flow direction and the location of the industrial station (S8), so it is expected to have considered changes only at station S5. Other studied stations along the branch hardly have any changes.

5.3.1.1 Salinity

Figure (5-33) show the salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the scenario No.1 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated a decrease at station S5 by about of 0, 0.25, 0.4 and 1.25 % in salinity concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C). The slight change in

salinity concentrations may be attributed to the low record of salinity at station (S8) according to the designed monitoring program.

Figure (5-33): Salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.1 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.1.2 Dissolved Oxygen

Figure (5-34) show the dissolved oxygen profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to scenario No.1 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an increase at station (S5) by about 138, 11, 8 and 47 % in DO concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C). The high change in DO concentrations happen in autumn that may be attributed to the low record of DO concentrations at station (S8) according to the designed monitoring program. Also, that shows the effect of increase the industrial effluents from the industrial companies at Kafr El-Zayat city in this season. The high significant enhancing for DO concentration (about 138%) during the autumn at (S5), which DO increases from 3.1 to 7.4 mg/l, that means it will be within the permissible limits (Law 48/1982). This may be attributed to the low record of DO at station (S8) according to the designed monitoring program.

Figure (5-34): DO profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.1 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.1.3 Biochemical Oxygen Demand

Figure (5-35) show the biochemical oxygen demand profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the scenario No. 1 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated a decrease at station (S5) by about 14, 0, 3 and 10 % in BOD concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C). There is no effect in BOD concentrations during the winter due to the value of BOD record was 0 mg/l at station (S8) according to the designed monitoring program.

Figure (5-35): BOD profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.1 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.1.4 Fecal Coliform

Figure (5-36) show the fecal coliform profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the scenario No.1 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated a decrease at station (S5) by about 33, 29, 15 and 3 % in FC concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C). The low enhancing for FC concentration during the summer at (S5), may be attributed to the low record of FC at station (S8) (800 N\100mL) according to the designed monitoring program.

Figure (5-36): FC profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of Scenario No.1 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.2 Scenario No.2: A 50% Reduction of the Salinity Concentrations of the Tala Drain Outlet

The scenario No.2 is to decrease the salinity concentrations of the Tala Drain outlet to the Rosetta Branch by 50% of the recorded concentrations of (2014-2015). This scenario can be conducted through discharging clean water to the Tala drain, using the modern irrigation system and reduction of the use of agricultural mineral fertilizers. According to the characteristics of the salinity

parameter as a conservative parameter, salinity parameter is the lone studied modeling parameter for this case.

5.3.2.1 Salinity

Figure (5-37) show the salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the Scenario No.2 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average decrease for the study area by about 28, 48, 47 and 49 % in salinity concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C). The figures indicated the negative impact of the Tala Drain on the Rosetta Branch. The salinity was recorded high concentrations (0.8 ppt) during different seasons at the Tala Drain outlet according to the designed monitoring program.

Figure (5-37): Salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.2 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.3 Scenario No.3: A 25% Reduction of the Tala Drain Discharge

The scenario No.3 is to decrease the water discharge of the Tala Drain to the Rosetta Branch by 25% of its recorded values. This scenario can be conducted through reusing wastewater to irrigate palm trees and non-edible

vegetation according to some proposed plans. The calibrated Rosetta Branch model was modified according to the studied scenario. The indicator parameters are salinity, dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and fecal coliform (FC).

5.3.3.1 Salinity

Figure (5-38) show the salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the Scenario No.3 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average decrease for the study area by about 1.5, 2.5, 3 and 4 % in salinity concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C). There is not a significant decrease in salinity changes in this scenario.

Figure (5-38): Salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.3 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.3.2 Dissolved Oxygen

Figures (5-39) show the dissolved oxygen profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the Scenario No.3 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average increase for the study area by about 48, 8, 0.1

and 22% in DO concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C). The high change for DO enhancing appears during autumn and summer. This is may be attributed to the high record of DO (12.3 mg\l) at the upstream of Tala Drain outlet (S1) during the autumn. While during the summer, this is may be attributed to the low record of DO (0.26 mg\l) at Tala Drain outlet (S2), according to the designed monitoring program.

Figure (5-39): DO profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.3 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.3.3 Biochemical Oxygen Demand

Figures (5-40) show the biochemical oxygen demand profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the scenario No.3 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average decrease for the study area by about 8, 31, 49 and 28 % in BOD concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C). The high change for BOD enhancing appears during the spring, may be attributed to the high record of BOD (14 mg\l) at Tala Drain outlet (S2), according to the designed monitoring program.

Figure (5-40): BOD profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.3 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.3.4 Fecal Coliform

Figures (5-41) show the fecal coliform profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the scenario No.3 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average decrease for the study area by about 5, 44, 16 and 14 % in FC concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C). The high change for FC enhancing appears during the winter, may be attributed to the low record of FC at the different monitoring stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city, according to the designed monitoring program.

Figure (5-41): FC profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.3 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.4 Scenario No.4: Diverting of the Tala Drain Discharge to the Nearest Main Drain

The scenario No.4 is based on stopping the domestic, agriculture wastewater and industrial effluent from the Tala Drain to the Rosetta Branch by diverting it to the nearest main drain. The calibrated Rosetta Branch model was modified according to the studied scenario. The indicator parameters are salinity, dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and fecal coliform (FC).

5.3.4.1 Salinity

Figures (5-42) show the salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the Scenario No.4 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average decrease for the study area by about 22, 50, 60 and 65 % in salinity concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C). The figures indicated the negative impact of the Tala Drain on the Rosetta Branch. The significant decrease in salinity concentrations may be attributed to stop agricultural fertilizer effluent to the Rosetta Branch by diverting the Tala Drain.

Figure (5-42): Salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.4 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.4.2 Dissolved Oxygen

Figures (5-43) show the dissolved oxygen profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the Scenario No.4 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average decrease for the study area by about 120, 35, 5 and 135 % in DO concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C). The significant increase in DO concentrations may be attributed to stop domestic and industrial effluent to the Rosetta Branch by diverting the Tala Drain.

Figure (5-43): DO profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.4 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.4.3 Biochemical Oxygen Demand

Figures (5-44) show the biochemical oxygen demand profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the Scenario No.4 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average decrease for the study area by about 37, 56, 61 and 58 % in BOD concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C). The significant decrease in BOD concentrations may be attributed to stop domestic effluent to the Rosetta Branch by diverting the Tala Drain.

Figure (5-44): BOD profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.4 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.4.4 Fecal Coliform

Figures (5-45) show the fecal coliform profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the Scenario No.4 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average decrease for the study area by about 66, 86, 81 and 87 % in FC concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C).

Figure (5-45): FC profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.4 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.5 Scenario No.5: A 25% Increase in the Rosetta Branch Discharge

The scenario No.5 is based on releasing more freshwater discharge in the study reach by about 25% in order to decrease the effect of pollution concentrations. The main concept is to dilute the organic load by increasing the Rosetta Branch discharge. The calibrated Rosetta Branch model was modified according to the studied scenario. The indicator parameters are salinity, dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and fecal coliform (FC).

5.3.5.1 Salinity

Figures (5-46) show the salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the Scenario No.5 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average decrease for the study area by about 1.3, 0.75, 1.5 and 1.25 % in salinity concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C). There is not a significant decrease in salinity changes for this scenario.

Figure (5-46): Salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.5 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.5.2 Dissolved Oxygen

Figures (5-47) show the dissolved oxygen profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the Scenario No.5 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average increase for the study area by about 57, 19, 6 and 75 % in DO concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C).

Figure (5-47): DO profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.5 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.5.3 Biochemical Oxygen Demand

Figures (5-48) show the biochemical oxygen demand profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the Scenario No.5 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average decrease for the study area by about 9, 38, 41 and 44 % in BOD concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C).

Figure (5-48): BOD profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.5 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.5.4 Fecal Coliform

Figures (5-49) show the fecal coliform profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the Scenario No.5 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average decrease for the study area by about 34, 43, 42 and 49 % in FC concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C).

Figure (5-49): FC profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.5 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.6 Scenario No.6: A 25% Decrease in the Rosetta Branch Discharge

The scenario No. 6 is based on reduction of the discharge in the study reach by about 25% in order to simulate the expected shortage in the River Nile water level. The probability of occurrence for this scenario is much expected due to the problem of water shortage that Egypt will suffer from it in the coming years. The calibrated Rosetta Branch model was modified according to the studied scenario. The indicator parameters are salinity, dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and fecal coliform (FC).

5.3.6.1 Salinity

Figures (5-46) show the salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the Scenario No.6 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average increase for the study area by about 1.5, 1, 2.5 and 3 % in salinity concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C). There is not a significant increase in salinity changes in this scenario.

Figure (5-50): Salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.6 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.6.2 Dissolved Oxygen

Figures (5-51) show the dissolved oxygen profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the Scenario No.6 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average decrease for the study area by about 10, 12, 2 and 44 % in DO concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C).

Figure (5-51): DO profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.6 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.6.3 Biochemical Oxygen Demand

Figures (5-52) show the biochemical oxygen demand profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the Scenario No.6 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average increase for the study area by about 1.5, 33, 34 and 40 % in BOD concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C).

Figure (5-52): BOD profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.6 compared to the simulated reference case

5.3.6.4 Fecal Coliform

Figures (5-53) show the fecal coliform profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer, as an example, due to applying of the Scenario No. 6 compared to the simulated reference case. The modeling results indicated an average increase for the study area by about 55, 72, 695 and 357 % in FC concentrations during autumn, winter, spring and summer, respectively. The results of other seasons can be seen in Appendix (C).

Figure (5-53): FC profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the summer due to applying of the Scenario No.6 compared to the simulated reference case

5.4 Feasibility of the Suggested Scenarios

Figures (5-54) – (5-57) show the average total changes for salinity, DO, BOD and FC for all scenarios, along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. Based on the presented results and the shown figures, it can be noticed the following:

5.4.1 The salinity

Scenarios No. 2 and No. 4 are the most effective scenarios for decreasing the salinity concentration by about 42 % and 49 %, respectively. The other scenarios have slight effects on salinity concentration. Scenario No.4, which is based on the diversion of the Tala Drain discharge to the nearest main drain, is the most effective scenario, as shown in Figure (5-54). Scenario No.1, which is based on the diversion of the industrial effluents to the city sewer system, has slight effect on salinity concentration at the downstream of the industrial companies of Kafr El-Zayat city (Station No.5) only. Scenario No.6, which is based on the reduction of the Rosetta Branch discharge by about 25%, has a negative effect on the salinity concentration with increasing by about 2 %.

Figure (5-54): The average percentage changes of the salinity for different water quality management scenarios for the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

5.4.2 Dissolved oxygen (DO)

Scenarios No.4 and No.5 are more effective than other scenarios for increasing the DO concentration at the study area along the Rosetta Branch by about 74 and 39 %, respectively. Scenario No.4, which is the diversion of the Tala Drain to the nearest main drain, is the most effective scenario, as shown in Figure (5-55). Scenarios No.1 effect on the downstream of the industrial companies of Kafr El-Zayat city only with a significant increase by about 51 %. Scenario No.6 has a negative effect on the DO concentration with decreasing by about 17 %.

Figure (5-55): The average percentage changes of DO for different water quality management scenarios for the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

5.4.3 Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD)

Scenarios No.3, No.4 and No.5 are more effective than other scenarios for decreasing the BOD concentration at the study area along the Rosetta Branch by about 29, 53 and 33 %, respectively. Scenario No.4, which is the diversion of the Tala Drain to the nearest main drain, is the most effective scenario, as shown in Figure (5-56). Scenario No.1 has a slight effect on the BOD concentration at the downstream of the industrial companies of Kafr El-Zayat city only with decrease by about 8 %. Scenario No.6 has a negative effect on the BOD concentration with increase by about 27 %.

Figure (5-56): The average percentage changes of BOD for different water quality management scenarios for the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

5.4.4 Fecal coliform (FC)

Scenarios No.4 and No.5 are more effective than other scenarios for decreasing the FC concentration at the study area along the Rosetta Branch by about 80 and 42 %, respectively. Scenario No.4, which is the diversion of the Tala Drain to the nearest main drain, is the most effective scenario, as shown in Figure (5-57). Scenario No.1 and No.3 have the same effect on the BOD concentration (about 20 %). Scenario No.1 effect on the downstream of the industrial companies of Kafr El-Zayat city only while scenario No.3 effect on the study area along the Rosetta Branch. Scenario No.6 has a negative significant effect on the BOD concentration with increase by about 300 %.

Figure (5-57): The average percentage changes of FC for different water quality management scenarios for the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

5.4.5 Summing up

Table (5-3) summarizes the results of the application of suggested management scenarios for the water quality status of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city, based on the developed water quality model.

Table (5-3): A summary of water quality management scenarios results along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city

Scenario Number	Description	The average percentage changes			
		Salinity	DO	BOD	FC
Scenario No.1	Diverting of the industrial effluents to the city sewer system	-0.5	51.0	-7.8	-20.0
Scenario No.2	Reduction of the salinity concentrations at the Tala Drain by 50%	-42.0	-	-	-
Scenario No.3	Reduction of the discharge at the Tala Drain by 25%	-2.8	19.8	-29.0	-19.8
Scenario No.4	Diverting of the Tala Drain discharge to the nearest main drain	-49.3	73.8	-53.0	-80.0
Scenario No.5	Increase of the discharge in the Rosetta Branch by 25%	-1.2	39.3	-33.0	-42.0
Scenario No.6	Reduction of the discharge in the Rosetta Branch by 25%	2.0	-17.0	27.3	299.3

The negative values in the Table (5-3) indicate to the average percentage reduction of water quality parameter values while positive values indicate to the average percentage increase of water quality parameter values.

From previous presented results of all management scenarios, it is clear that the behavior of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city response to varying in water quality conditions. Scenario No.5 which represents the increase of discharge in the Rosetta Branch by about 25%, does not affect the significant impact on the quality of water in the branch, compared to the best scenario (Scenario No.4).

Scenario No.4, which represents the diversion of the Tala Drain to the nearest main drain, appears the most effective scenario. It has significant impact on the study reach water quality parameter. However, an integrated approach would be needed for the management of study reach water quality based on the application of Tala Drain diversion and innovation of appropriate ways to dispose the agricultural, industrial and domestic wastewater which are alternative to the Tala Drain.

Scenario No.6, which is based on the reduction of the Rosetta Branch discharge by about 25%, has a negative effect on water quality of the Rosetta Branch. These confirm that the expected decreasing in the water level of the River Nile will cause deterioration in water quality of the Rosetta Branch in the next few years.

Chapter (6)

CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Introduction

The main objective of this research work is investigating the water quality management of the Rosetta Branch which represents the main source of fresh water for drinking, irrigation, and industrial activities in the Nile Delta of Egypt. For this, the Rosetta Branch reach at Kafr El-Zayat city, including Tala Drain outlet and the industrial area, was selected as a study area for this study. Water samples from eight monitoring stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city and from the Tala Drain, were seasonally collected and analyzed. A GIS database was established to arrange, manage and present the spatial distribution of the collected data from the study area. A hydrodynamic and ecological model was developed, based on MIKE11 modeling code, to simulate the hydrodynamic and water quality processes of the branch. The developed model was used to investigate some feasible water quality mitigation scenarios for water quality control in Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. Moreover, water quality index and statistical analysis approaches were applied to assess the water quality status of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city.

In this chapter, conclusions are drawn about the achievements of this research work. Recommendations are proposed and future research issues are also indicated.

6.2 Conclusions

6.2.1 Water quality monitoring program for the Rosetta Branch

Water samples from eight monitoring stations along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city and from the Tala Drain, were seasonally collected and analyzed during the period from November 2014 to August 2015. The records were compared to the Egyptian water quality standards for fresh waterways, decree No. 49 – Law 48/1982 – Article No. 60 amended in 2013. According to the analysis of the collected records, it can be concluded the following:

- 1) Along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city, most of the recorded parameters: water temperature, turbidity, TDS, SO₄, PO₄, Fe, Mn and nitrogen components, were within the permissible limits.
- 2) The maximum records of BOD, COD are greater than the higher limit of the standard at the considered stations along the Rosetta Branch. While during summer 2015, the minimum records of DO are less than the lower limit of the standard and maximum records of fecal coliform are greater than the higher limit of the standard.
- 3) For the Tala drain, the collected records from its outlet showed that the critical parameters were TDS, DO, BOD, COD, FC and PO₄. The records of DO and FC were significantly out of the permissible limit during summer 2015. All other records of the critical parameters exceed the permissible limit for all studied seasons.
- 4) The worst water quality conditions were recorded during autumn 2014 and summer 2015 seasons.

- 5) A serious ecological problem occurs during summer; the field records of this study confirmed the phenomenon of the death of fish (Fish kill) in the Rosetta Branch due to the dissolved oxygen depletion.

6.2.2 Water quality assessment of the Rosetta Branch

Two water quality indices (CCMEWQI and NSFWQI) were used to assess the water quality status of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city, based on field records during the period from November 2014 to August 2015. The Egyptian water quality standards for fresh waterways, decree No. 49 – Law 48/1982 – Article No. 60 amended in 2013, were considered in CCME WQI. Moreover, two statistical analysis approaches, correlation analysis and factor analysis (FA) /principle component analysis (PCA), were developed to obtain the nature of correlations among the different parameters and to identify the significant sources of water pollution and to isolate the impact of each parameter on a mass loading in the study area during the same period.

Based on the water quality assessment results, it can be concluded that:

- 1) NSFWQI results, the water quality status of the study area varied from “Good” to “Medium” for all studied seasons. Except for summer 2015, water quality status was hardly “Medium” and “Bad” at the downstream of the industrial area and the Tala Drain outlet, respectively.
- 2) CCMEWQI results confirmed the same findings of the NSFWQI for the study area where the water quality status of the study area varied from “Excellent” to “Marginal” for all studied seasons. Except for summer 2015, water quality status ranged from “Fair” to “Marginal”, in particular at the downstream of the industrial area (Marginal) and at the Tala Drain outlet (Poor).

- 3) The results of WQIs also showed that water temperature, DO and FC were the effective parameters which lead to poor or bad water quality status along the Rosetta Branch during summer 2015.
- 4) A correlation matrix results showed that very strong correlation were found correlation TDS, salinity and conductivity; strong correlation between NO_2 and NO_3 ; moderate correlation between FC and DO.
- 5) Using factor analysis / principal component analysis, the number of recorded water quality parameters was reduced to 5 water quality attributes; these 5 attributes explained about 83 % of the total variance.
- 6) The five components from factor analysis highlighted that agricultural drainage is the dominant water quality issue for the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city, its variance was about 34%. Municipal and biological pollution were the second water quality issue, its variance was about 18%.
- 7) The statistical analysis results indicated that the water quality status of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city was mainly regulated by salinity, DO, pH, BOD, COD, FC and nutrients component.

6.2.3 Hydro-ecological modeling of the Rosetta Branch

A hydro-ecological model for the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city was developed. The water flow and water quality processes of Rosetta branch could be successfully simulated using MIKE 11 water quality model. The main objective of this simulation is to test and evaluate the different scenarios for improving the water quality status of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city. Three hydrodynamic parameters (water levels, water temperature and salinity) and three water quality characteristics (DO, BOD and FC) were

simulated. The model was calibrated using water quality records from November 2014 to August 2015.

Based on the presented results, it can be concluded that the calibration process can be considered as acceptable; a good agreement between the measured records and simulated results was noticed. Small AME and RMSE values were recorded; the average AME values for water temperature, salinity, DO and BOD were 0.12 °C, 0.04 ppt, 0.65 and 0.66 mg/l, respectively. Their similar average RMSE values were 0.13 °C, 0.05 ppt, 0.78 and 0.93 mg/l, respectively.

The suggested management scenarios for improving the water quality of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city were applied:

- (i) Diverting of the industrial effluents to the city sewer system (as planned) (Scenario No.1).
- (ii) Reduction of the salinity concentrations of the Tala Drain by 50% (Scenarios No. 2).
- (iii) Reduction of the discharge of the Tala Drain by 25% (Scenarios No. 3).
- (iv) Diverting of the Tala Drain discharge to the nearest main drain (Scenarios No. 4).
- (v) Releasing of more freshwater discharge in the Rosetta Branch by 25% (Scenarios No. 5).
- (vi) Reduction of the discharge in the Rosetta Branch by 25% (Scenarios No. 6).

According to the results of alternative scenarios for water quality management, it can be reported the following:

- 1) Scenario No.1 affects the water quality status of the downstream reach of the industrial companies outlet; an increase by about 51% in the average DO concentration was noticed.
- 2) Scenario No.2 reduced the average salinity concentrations along the studied reach of the Rosetta Branch by about 42%.
- 3) Scenario No.3 slightly affect the water quality status of the Rosetta Branch; an increase by about 20% in the average DO concentration and reductions by about 29 and 20% in the averages of BOD and FC concentrations, respectively, were noticed.
- 4) Scenario No.4 appears the most effective scenario. It has the most significant impact on the water quality status of the branch; an increase by about 74% in the average DO concentration and reductions by about 49, 53 and 80% in the averages of salinity, BOD and FC concentrations, respectively, were noticed.
- 5) Scenario No.5 has a small effect on the water quality status of the Rosetta Branch; an increase by about 39% in the average DO concentration and reductions by about 33 and 42% in the averages of BOD and FC concentrations, respectively, were noticed.
- 6) Scenario No.6 has a negative effect on the water quality status of the Rosetta Branch. This confirms that the expected decrease in the water discharge of the River Nile will cause deterioration in its water quality status in the next few years.
- 7) It can be concluded that a full control of the studied point sources effluents (the Tala drain and the industrial companies' outlets), will lead to a significant improve of the water quality status of the Rosetta Branch.

6.3 Recommendations

Based on the study results, the recommendations for future research work, to improve the integrated management for the Rosetta Branch, are as follows:

- Urgent water quality management plans are essential for the Rosetta Branch to maintain pollution levels within the permissible values, to satisfy both human needs and the ecological balance in the river system.
- There is a need for an intensive monitoring program of water quality for the Rosetta Branch to detect changes in its water quality status, which is mainly used for drinking purpose.
- A treatment plant should be installed at the outlet of the Tala Drain and the industrial companies to enhance its water quality before discharging its effluents in the Rosetta Branch.
- Investigating of the economic study to divert the industrial effluents of the industrial companies at Kafr El-Zayat to the city sewer system and divert the Tala Drain discharge to the nearest main drain.
- It should be considered the presented results of statistical analysis to select appropriate water quality parameters, which will be used in water quality indices.
- An integration utilization of the remote sensing technologies should be applied to overcome the limitation of data and provide accurate spatial and temporal distribution of data
- A detailed sediment transport model should be developed to avoid causing local erosion and accesion problems.
- Searching for application of the Egyptian Water Quality Index including how the challenge of the scarcity of use based water quality guidelines was overcome.

References

1. Abbasi, Tasneem and Shahid A. Abbasi (2012). Water quality indices. Elsevier.
2. Abdel-Satar, A. and A. Elewa (2001). Water quality and environmental assessments of the River Nile at Rossetta Branch. In: The second International Conference and Exhibition for life and Environment, Alexandria, 3-5, 136-164., 2001. pp 3-5.
3. Abdel-Satar A, Goher M, Sayed M (2010). Recent environmental changes in water and sediment quality of Lake Qarun, Egypt Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Science 5:56-69.
4. Abdel-Satar AM (2005). Water quality assessment of river Nile from Idfo to Cairo Egyptian Journal of Aquatic Research 31:200-223.
5. Abdo M (2013). Physico-Chemeical Studies on the Pollutants Effect in the Aquatic Environment of Rosetta Branch River Nile, Egypt Life Science Journal.
6. Abdo M, Sabae S, Haroon B, Refaat B, Mohammed A (2010). Physico-chemical characteristics, microbial assessment and antibiotic susceptibility of pathogenic bacteria of Ismailia canal water, River Nile, Egypt J Am Sci 6:234-250.
7. Abdo MH (2002). Environmental studies on Rosetta branch and some chemical applications at the area extend from El-Kanater El-Khyria to Kafr-El-Zyat City. Ph D Thesis, Fac of Sci Ain Shams Univ, Cairo, Egypt.
8. Abou El-Gheit E, Abdo MH, SA M (2012). Impacts of Blooming Phenomenon on Water Quality and Fishes in Quarun Lake, Egypt International Journal of Environmental Science and Engineering 3:11-23.
9. Agrama A (2012). Assessment of Surface Water Quality in Egypt, Environment and Climate changes Research Institute, National Water Research Center, El-Qanater El-Khairiya, P.O. B. 13621/5, Egypt. Journal of Applied Sciences Research, 8(4): 1944-1951.
10. Ahmed N (2007). Effect of River Nile pollution on Clarias gariepinus located between El-Kanater El-Khayria and Helwan. M. Sc. Thesis, Faculty of Agriculture, Zagazig Univ..

11. Ahmed N (2012). Biochemical studies on pollution of the River Nile at different stations of delta barrage (Egypt). Ph. D. thesis. Fac. of Agric. Benha Univ..
12. Alawy AE, El-TRAS WF, khater DF, El Raiy HR (2015). Impact of industrial wastewater on water and fish quality of Nile River in Kafr El-Zayat, Egypt Benha Veterinary Medical Journal, Vol 28.
13. Alves MTR, Teresa FB, Nabout JC (2014). A global scientific literature of research on water quality indices: trends, biases and future directions *Acta Limnologica Brasiliensia* 26:245-253.
14. Ambrose R, Wool T, Martin J (1993). WASP 5, The Water Quality Analysis Simulation Program Version 5.00 ASCI Corporation, Athens, Georgia.
15. APHA (2005). Standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater Federation, Water Environmental American Public Health Association (APHA): Washington, DC, USA.
16. Bartram J, Ballance R (1996). Water quality monitoring: a practical guide to the design and implementation of freshwater quality studies and monitoring programmes. CRC Press.
17. Bharti N, Katyal D (2011). Water quality indices used for surface water vulnerability assessment *International Journal of Environmental Sciences*
18. Biswas AK, Tortajada C (2009). Changing global water management landscape. In: *Water management in 2020 and beyond*. Springer.
19. Boyacioglu H (2006). Surface water quality assessment using factor analysis *Water SA* 32:389-393.
20. Boyd C (2000). *Water quality: an introduction*. Kluwer Academic Publishers Norwell, Boston, Mass ; London, pp. 330.
21. Brown LC, Barnwell TO (1987). The enhanced stream water quality models QUAL2E and QUAL2E-UNCAS: Documentation and user manual. US Environmental Protection Agency. Office of Research and Development. Environmental Research Laboratory.
22. Brown P, El Gohary F, Tawfic MA, Hamdy EI, Abdel-Gawad S (2003). Nile River Water Quality Management Study. United States Agency for International Development/Egypt, Ed. Cairo, Egypt: Egypt Water Policy Reform.

23. Brown RM, McClelland NI, Deininger RA, Tozer RG (1970). A Water Quality Index- Do We Dare? *Water Sewage Works*, 117: 339-343.
24. CCME (2001). Canadian water quality guidelines for the protection of aquatic life., CCME water quality index 1.0 Technical Report. Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment.
25. CCME (2004). CCME National Water Quality Index Workshop, Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment.
26. Chambers JM (1983) Graphical methods for data analysis. Wadsworth International Group, Belmont, CA.
27. Chapman (1996). *Water Quality Assessments - A Guide to Use of Biota, Sediments and Water in Environmental Monitoring* (World Health Organization) -Second Edition.
28. Chapra SC (2008). *Surface water-quality modeling*. Waveland press, McGraw-Hill, New York, pp. 844.
29. Costello A, Osborne J (2011). Best practices in exploratory factor analysis: four recommendations for getting the most from your analysis. *Pract Assess Res Eval* 2005.
30. Cox B (2003). A review of currently available in-stream water-quality models and their applicability for simulating dissolved oxygen in lowland rivers *Science of the Total Environment* 314:335-377.
31. Daboor S (2006). *Studies on Bacterial Flora and Its Role in the Clean-up of Hazardous Pollutants in the River Nile*. Ph. D. Thesis (Botany), Faculty of Science, Zagazig Univ., Egypt.
32. Dahl M, Wilson D (2001). *Modelling of water quality*. Karlstad University Sweden.
33. Daifullah A, Elewa A, Shehata M, Abdo M (2003). Evaluation of some heavy metals in water, sediment and fish samples from River Nile(Kafr El-Zyat City), Egypt: a treatment approach *African journal of environmental assessment and management* 6:16-31.
34. Demirel Z, Ozer Z, Ozpinar Z, Gulcicek O (2007) *The Application of GIS and Models on the Water Basin Management – A Case Study Of Berdan River*.
35. DHI (2012) Danish Hydraulic Institute. MIKE 11 - User Guide and Technical Reference Manual. DHI Water & Environment, Denmark.

36. Donia N. (2005). Rosetta branch waste load allocation model. In: 9th International Water Technology Conference, Sharm El-Sheikh. pp 7-20.
37. Donia N., El-Azizy I., Khalifa A. (2003). Industrial pollution control of Rosetta branch, Nile River, EGYPT. In: the Proceedings of the Seventh Intl. Water Technol. Conference, Egypt. pp 235-247.
38. Donigan AS, Imhoff JC, Bicknell BR, Kittle JL (1984). Application Guide for Hydrological Simulation Program: FORTRAN(HSPF) EPA-600/3-84-065 June 1984 Environmental Research Laboratory, Athens, GA 177 p, 19 fig, 17 tab, 3 app, 20 ref 68-01-6207.
39. Edejer T-T, Baltussen R, Adam T, Hutubessy R, Acharya A, Evans D, Murray C (2003). WHO guide to cost-effectiveness analysis Geneva: World Health Organization.
40. EEAA (2007). Egyptian Environmental Affairs Agency: Egypt State of the Environment Report2007, 2008, p. 94.:94
41. EEAA (2010). Egypt Environmental Affairs Agency–EEAA- Egypt second national communication under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate change. Egypt Environmental Affairs Agency, Cairo.
42. Effendi H, Wardiatno Y (2015). Water quality status of Ciambulawung River, Banten Province, based on pollution index and NSF-WQI *Procedia Environmental Sciences* 24:228-237.
43. Eisakhani M, Abdullah MP, Karim OA, Malakahmad A (2012). Validation of MIKE 11 model simulated data for biochemical and chemical oxygen demands transport *American Journal of Applied Sciences* 9:382.
44. El-Amier YA, Zahran MAE-K, Al-Mamory SH (2015). Assessment the Physico-Chemical Characteristics of Water and Sediment in Rosetta Branch, *Egypt Journal of Water Resource and Protection* 7:1075.
45. El-Bahrawy N, Abu Elaa S (2002). Pollution in the Nile River: Assessment and Control Case Study. In: Nile 2002 International Conference on Comprehensive Resources Development in the River Basin, Cairo, Egypt.
46. El-Bouraié M, El-Barbary A, Yehia M, Motawea E (2010). Heavy metal concentrations in surface river water and bed sediments at Nile Delta in Egypt *Suo* 61:1-12.

47. El-Gamal A, Shafik Y (1985). Monitoring of pollutants discharging to the river Nile and their effect on river water quality Water Quality Bulletin.
48. El-Sadek A (2005) Climate change impacts on the water quality: A case study of the Rosetta Branch in the Nile Delta, Egypt National Water Research Center, Egypt.
49. El-Sadek A, Radwan M, Willems P (2011). Mathematical Modeling of Nitrate and Salinity along the Rosetta Branch in the Nile Delta Arab Gulf Journal of Scientific Research 29:1-10.
50. El-Sayed S (2011). Physicochemical studies on the impact of pollution up on the River Nile branches, Egypt. M. Sc. Thesis Faculty of Science, Benha University, Egypt.
51. El Gammal H, El Shazely H (2008). Water quality management scenarios in Rosetta river Nile branch, Egypt. In: Twelfth International Water Technology Conference, IWTC12, Citeseer.
52. El Gohary R (2015). Agriculture, industry, and wastewater in the Nile Delta. International Journal of Scientific Research in Agricultural Sciences, 2 (Proceedings):159-172.
53. Elewa , Shehata MB, Mohamed LF, Badr MH, GS A-A (2009). Water Quality Characteristics of the the River Nile at Delta Barrage with Special Reference to the Rosetta Branch. Global Journal of Environmental Research.
54. Elewa H, El Nahry A (2009). Hydro-environmental status and soil management of the River Nile Delta, Egypt Environmental Geology 57:759.
55. Elshemy MM (2010). Water Quality Modeling of Large Reservoirs in Semi-arid Regions Under Climate Change: Example Lake Nasser (Egypt).
56. Erez J, Krom M, Neuwirth T (1990). Daily oxygen variations in marine fish ponds, Aquaculture 84:289-305.
57. Ezzat SM, Mahdy HM, Abo-State MA, Abd El Shakour EH, El-Bahnasawy MA (2012). Water quality assessment of river Nile at Rosetta branch: impact of drains discharge Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research 12:413-423.
58. Gandolfi C, Kraszewski A, Sessa RS (1996) River water quality modeling. In: Environmental Hydraulics. Springer, pp 245-288.

59. Garizi AZ, Sheikh V, Sadoddin A (2011). Assessment of seasonal variations of chemical characteristics in surface water using multivariate statistical methods *International Journal of Environmental Science & Technology* 8:581-592.
60. Ghallab M (2000). Some physical and chemical changes on River Nile down stream of Delta Barrage at El-Rahawy drain. M. Sc. Thesis Fac. of Sci. Ain Shams Univ. Cairo, Egypt.
61. Han S, Kim E, Kim S (2009). The water quality management in the Nakdong River watershed using multivariate statistical techniques *KSCE Journal of Civil Engineering* 13:97-105.
62. Hanley N, Faichney R, Munro A, Shortle JS (1998). Economic and environmental modelling for pollution control in an estuary *Journal of Environmental Management* 52:211-225.
63. Heikal M, El-Sherbini A, Salem T, Yousry (2007). M Temporal and spatial variation of water quality parameters along the River Nile. In: NAWQAM Final Conference on Egypt Paradigm in Integrated Water Resources Management, February. pp 17-19.
64. Horton RK (1965). An index number system for rating water quality. *Journal of Water Pollution Control Federation* 37:300-306.
65. House MA (1989). A water quality index for river management. *Water and Environment Journal* 3:336-344.
66. Ibrahim SA (2013). Effect of water quality changes on gills and kidney histology of *Oreochromis niloticus* fish inhabiting the water of Rosetta Branch, River Nile, Egypt *World Applied Sciences. J* 26:438-448.
67. Iyer CP, Sindhu M, Kulkarni SG, Tambe SS, Kulkarni BD (2003). Statistical analysis of the physico-chemical data on the coastal waters of Cochin. *Journal of Environmental Monitoring.* 5:324-327.
68. Jakovljević D (2012). Serbian and Canadian water quality index of Danube River in Serbia in 2010 *Geogr Inst Cvijic.* 62:1-18.
69. Jolliffe I (2002). *Principal component analysis.* Wiley Online Library.
70. Kathuria V (2006). Controlling water pollution in developing and transition countries lessons from three successful cases. *Journal of Environmental Management.* 78:405-426.

71. Kebede YK (2012). Application of principal component analysis in surface water quality monitoring Principal Component Analysis-Engineering Applications, P Sanguansat, Ed:83-100.
72. Khan AA, Abdel-Gawad S, Khan H (2008). A Real Time Water Quality Monitoring Network and Water Quality Indices for River Nile. In: 13th IWRA World Water Congress 2008.
73. Khan AA, Tobin A, Paterson R, Khan H, Warren R (2005). Application of CCME procedures for deriving site-specific water quality guidelines for the CCME Water Quality Index. Water Quality Research Journal of Canada.
74. Khandan N (2001). Modeling tools for environmental engineers and scientists. CRC Press.
75. Khatoon N, Khan AH, Rehman M, Pathak V (2013). Correlation study for the assessment of water quality and its parameters of Ganga River, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India J Appl Chem 5:80-90.
76. Khopkar S (2007). Environmental pollution monitoring and control. New Age International.
77. Korium M, Toufeek M (2008). Studies of some physicochemical characteristics of old Aswan Dam Reservoir and River Nile water at Aswan.
78. Kumar A, Sharma M, Yadav NS (2014). Assessment of Water Quality Changes at Two Locations of Chambal River: MP Journal of Materials and Environmental Science 5:1781-1785.
79. Kumar D, Alappat BJ (2009). NSF-Water Quality Index: Does It Represent the Experts' Opinion? Practice Periodical of Hazardous, Toxic, and Radioactive Waste Management 13:75-79.
80. Kumar M, Ramanathan A, Rao M, Kumar B (2006). Identification and evaluation of hydrogeochemical processes in the groundwater environment of Delhi, India Environmental Geology 50:1025-1039.
81. Lehr JH, Keeley JW, Lehr JK, Kingery TB (2005). Water encyclopedia. John Wiley & Sons.
82. Liang J, Yang Q, Sun T, Martin J, Sun H, Li L (2015). MIKE 11 model-based water quality model as a tool for the evaluation of water quality management plans Journal of Water Supply: Research and Technology-Aqua

83. Liou S-M, Lo S-L, Wang S-H (2004). A generalized water quality index for Taiwan Environmental monitoring and assessment 96:35-52.
84. Liu C-W, Lin K-H, Kuo Y-M (2003). Application of factor analysis in the assessment of groundwater quality in a blackfoot disease area in Taiwan Science of the Total Environment 313:77-89.
85. Madsen MN, Jensen LN, Wood DM, Parkinson DS, Parkinson S, Myers R (2001). Modelling of water temperature and total dissolved gas in the Snake River below the Hells Canyon Dam, Idaho.
86. MADWQ (2000). Monitoring and Analysis of Drainage Water Quality Project, Report no. 60.
87. Mahmoud S, Tayel S, Yacoub A (2008). Histopathological changes in kidneys of the fish *Tilapia zillii*:219-246.
88. Maidment DR (2002). Arc Hydro: GIS for water resources vol 1. ESRI, Inc.
89. Mashali S, El-Essawi T, Youssif T, Hafz O (2009). Effect of Different Industrial Wastes on Soil Quality at Different Locations of Egypt.
90. Mazlum N, OZER A, MAZLUM S (1999). Interpretation of water quality data by principal components analysis Turkish Journal of Engineering and Environmental Sciences 23:19-26.
91. Metawea EAA (2009). Monitoring and evaluation of some chemical parameters associated with changing the effluent rates on El-Rahawy drain and their impact on water quality of Rosetta branch. MSc Thesis Fac. Sci. Cairo Univ. Egypt.
92. Mohamed FA, Gad NS (2008). Environmental pollution-induced biochemical changes in tissues of *Tilapia zillii*, *Solea vulgaris* and *Mugil capito* from Lake Qarun, Egypt. Global Vet 2:327-336.
93. Mohamed HEd (2008). Assessment of Environmental Pollution Sources and its Impact on Rosetta Branch Water Quality Ain Shams University Institute of Environmental Studies & Research Department of Biological and Physical Sciences.
94. Mojahedi SA, Attari J (2009). A comparative study of water quality indices for Karun River. In: World Environmental and Water Resources Congress.

95. Mostafa M (2014). Modeling of Pollutant Transport in the Nile Delta Egypt. Ph. D. Dissertation. University of Alabama at Birmingham, Birmingham.
96. Mostafa M, Peters RW (2016). A Comprehensive Assessment of Water Quality at the Rosetta Branch of the Nile River, Egypt .
97. Mostafa MK (2015). Impact of Improving Water Quality at the Tala Drain on the Rosetta Branch Water Quality Journal of Environmental Protection.
98. Moustafa M, Mohamed H, Amal M, Talat M, Siliem M (2010). Water Quality Assessment of Rosetta and Damietta Branches, River Nile, Egypt. African Journal of Biological Sciences 6:127-142.
99. MWRI (2002). Ministry of Water Resources and Irrigation, Egypt, APRP Water, Policy Program 2002, Report No. 64, "Survey of Nile System Pollution Sources".
100. MWRI (2003) Ministry of Water Resources and Irrigation, Egypt Water Policy Reform 2003, Report No. 67, "Nile River Water Quality Management Study".
101. MWRI (2005). Water for the Future, National Water Resources Plan for Egypt - 2017: Egyptian Ministry of Water Resources and Irrigation.
102. Navidi WC (2010). Principles of statistics for engineers and scientists. McGraw-Hill New York.
103. NBI (2005) Nile Basin Initiative, "Nile Basin National Water Quality Monitoring Baseline Study Report for Egypt", The Nile Transboundary Environmental Action Project (NTEAP).
104. Neswiswi AB (2015). Development of water quality index (WQI) for the Juskei River catchment, Johannesburg.
105. NRC (2001). National Research Council. Assessing the TMDL approach to water quality management committee to assess the scientific basis of the total maximum daily load approach to water pollution reduction. Washington, D.C., Water Science and Technology Board, National Academy Press.
106. Oprean LI, Chicea D, Gaspar E, Lengyel E (2008). Results of physical and chemical parameters monitoring of the "Râul Mare" river Rom Journ Phys 53:947-953.

107. Osman AG, Kloas W (2010). Water quality and heavy metal monitoring in water, sediments, and tissues of the African catfish *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell, 1822) from the river Nile, Egypt *Journal of Environmental Protection* 1:389.
108. Osman M, Mohamed A, Ali M, Al-Afify A (2010). Assessment of agriculture drainage water quality to be used for fish farm irrigation *Nature and Science* 8:60-74.
109. Othman Sae-a, Kandil AT, Elsaadi AmK (2009). Evaluation of the water quality in the southern part of rosetta branch Thesis (master)-helwan university faculty of science department of Chemistry.
110. Palmer MD (2001). Water quality modeling: a guide to effective practice. World bank publications.
111. Parizi HS, Samani N (2013). Geochemical evolution and quality assessment of water resources in the Sarcheshmeh copper mine area (Iran) using multivariate statistical techniques *Environmental earth sciences*.
112. Parrish JB, Burt CM (1993). Cal Poly model canal *Journal of irrigation and drainage engineering* 119:673-678.
113. Pollard S, Du Toit D (2008). Integrated water resource management in complex systems: How the catchment management strategies seek to achieve sustainability and equity in water resources in South Africa *Water SA* 34:671-679.
114. Poonam T, Tanushree B, Sukalyan C (2013). Water quality indices - important tools for water quality assessment: a review *International Journal of Advances in Chemistry* 1:15-28.
115. Postma L (1990). Delft Water Quality model-DELWAQ Delft Hydraulics Program Manual.
116. Radwan M (2009). Global warming impacts on water quality in the Nile Delta, Egypt *Nile Basin Water Engineering Scientific Magazine* 2:71-78.
117. Ray S, Bari S, Shuvro S (2015). Assessment of Water Quality of Goalichara: A Water Quality Index Based Approach *relation* 2:3.
118. Razdar B, Mohammadi K, Samani J, Pirooz B (2011). Determining the best water quality model for the rivers in north of Iran (case study: Pasikhan River) *Computational Methods in Civil Engineering* 2:105-116.

119. Reckhow KH, Chapra SC (1983). Engineering approaches for lake management vol 1. Butterworth Boston, MA.
120. Reda M, Mohamed SAE-F, Riad P, El Gammal H, El Deen MN (2015). Modeling Surface Water Quality Upstream Cairo Drinking Water Plants. *New York Science Journal* 2015;8(5).
121. Reghunath R, Murthy TS, Raghavan B (2002). The utility of multivariate statistical techniques in hydrogeochemical studies: an example from Karnataka, India *Water research* 36:2437-2442.
122. Reichert P (1998). AQUASIM 2.0-user manual Swiss Federal Institute for Environmental Science and Technology Dübendorf, Switzerland.
123. Rnjbar Jafarabadi A, Masoodi M, Sharifiniya M, Riyahi Bakhtiyari A (2016). Integrated river quality management by CCME WQI as an effective tool to characterize surface water source pollution (Case study: Karun River, Iran) *Pollution* 2:313-330.
124. Saad SMM, A.E.; E-D, and TSI, N.A.M. A (2011). Haematological and histopathological studies on *Clarias gariepinus* in relation to water quality along Rosetta branch, River Nile, Egypt. *The Egyptian Journal of Experimental Biology (Zoology)* 7:223-233.
125. Samia Mohamed (2013). Surface Water Quality Management Case Study: Rosetta Branch-River Nile. PhD Degree of Science in Civil Engineering (Irrigation and Hydraulics) Ain Shams University.
126. Sarkar S, Mishra U (2014) Analysis on Water Quality of Haora River in Agartala with an Assessment of Water Quality Index *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, ISSN:0973-4562
127. Sayed MF (2003). Chemical studies on pollution in Rosetta branch of River Nile between Kafr El-Zayat and Rosetta outlet. PhD Thesis, Fac Sci, Cairo Univ Egypt, pp: 403.
128. Schnoor JL (1996). Environmental modeling: fate and transport of pollutants in water, air, and soil. John Wiley and Sons.
129. Scott A, Jirka G (2002). Environmental fluid mechanisms part I: Mass transfer and diffusion Karlsruhe, Germany.
130. Sharma D, Kansal A (2011). Water quality analysis of River Yamuna using water quality index in the national capital territory, India (2000–2009) *Applied Water Science* 1:147-157.

131. Shehata S, Badr S (2010). Water Quality Changes in River Nile Cairo, Egypt *Journal of Applied Sciences Research* 6:1457-1465.
132. Shokuhi R, Hosinzadeh E, Roshanaei G, Alipour M, Hoseinzadeh S (2012). Evaluation of Aydughmush dam reservoir water quality by National Sanitation Foundation Water Quality Index (NSF-WQI) and water quality parameter changes *Iranian Journal of Health and Environment* 4:439-450.
133. Shrestha S, Kazama F (2007). Assessment of surface water quality using multivariate statistical techniques: A case study of the Fuji river basin, *Japan Environmental Modelling & Software* 22:464-475.
134. Sigeo D, Microbiology F (2005). Biodiversity and Dynamic Interactions of Microorganisms in the Aquatic Environment *Freshwater Microbiology*, John Wiley & Sons Ltd:1s68-176.
135. Simeonov V, Einax J, Stanimirova I, Kraft J (2002). Environmetric modeling and interpretation of river water monitoring data *Analytical and bioanalytical chemistry* 374:898-905.
136. Simeonov V et al. (2003). Assessment of the surface water quality in Northern Greece *Water research* 37:4119-4124.
137. Simoes F, Moreira AB, Bisinoti MC, Gimenez SMN, Yabe MJS (2008). Water quality index as a simple indicator of aquaculture effects on aquatic bodies *Ecological indicators* 8:476-484.
138. Singovszka E, Balintova M (2012). Application factor analysis for the evaluation surface water and sediment quality *chemical engineering*.
139. Smith DG (1990). A better water quality indexing system for rivers and streams *Water research* 24:1237-1244.
140. Socolofsky SA, Jirka GH (2002). *Environmental Fluid Mechanics Part I: Mass Transfer and Diffusion Class notes*.
141. Strobl R, Robillard P, Shannon R, Day R, McDonnell A (2006). A water quality monitoring network design methodology for the selection of critical sampling points: Part I *Environmental monitoring and assessment*.
142. Tayel S, Yacoub A, Mahmoud S (2008). Histopathological and haematological responses to freshwater pollution in the Nile catfish *Clarias gariepinus*. *Journal of Egyptian Academic Society for Environmental Development* 9:43-60.

143. Thivya C, Chidambaram S, Thilagavathi R, Prasanna M, Singaraja C, Nepolian M, Sundararajan M (2014). Identification of the geochemical processes in groundwater by factor analysis in hard rock aquifers of Madurai District, South India. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences* 7:3767-3777.
144. Thomann RV, Mueller JA (1987). Principles of surface water quality modeling and control. Harper & Row, Publishers.
145. Tyagi S, Sharma B, Singh P, Dobhal R (2013). Water quality assessment in terms of water quality index. *American Journal of Water Resources* 1:34-38
146. Valecha V, Bhatnagar G (1988). Seasonal changes of phytoplankton in relation to some physicochemical factors in lower lake of Bhopal Geobios.
147. Vieira DA, Wu W (2002). One-Dimensional Channel Network Model CCHE1D Version 3.0 æ User's Manual.
148. Vigil KM (2003). Clean water As Introduction to Water Quality and Water Pollution Control.
149. Wahaab RA (1995). Wastewater treatment and reuse: environmental health and safety considerations *International Journal of Environmental Health Research*.
150. Wahaab RA, Badawy MI (2004). Water quality assessment of the River Nile system: an overview *Biomedical and environmental sciences* 17:87-100.
151. Wang Y et al. (2013). Assessment of surface water quality via multivariate statistical techniques: a case study of the Songhua River Harbin region, China *Journal of Hydro-Environment Research* 7:30-40.
152. Weiner R, Matthews R (2003). Environmental engineering. Butterworth-Heinemann.
153. Wells SA, Cole TM (2000). Theoretical basis for the CE-QUAL-W2 river basin model. DTIC Document.
154. Whiteaker TL, Maidment DR, Goodall JL, Takamatsu M (2006). Integrating Arc Hydro features with a schematic network *Transactions in GIS*.

155. Wu W, Vieira DA, Wang SS (2004). One-dimensional numerical model for nonuniform sediment transport under unsteady flows in channel networks *Journal of Hydraulic Engineering* 130:914-923.
156. WWAP (2006). World Water Assessment Programme, A Shared Responsibility. The United Nations World Water Development Report 2. UNESCO, Paris.
157. Yousry M, Awadallah A, Salem T (2011). Assessment of Nile water quality data using exploratory data analysis and clustering of variables *Geoscience Research*.

Appendices

- **Appendix A:** The calculations, tables and curves of water quality indices
- **Appendix B:** Cross sections of study area along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city using GIS.
- **Appendix C:** The results of water quality mitigation scenarios.

Appendix A: The calculations, tables and curves of water quality indices

National Sanitation Foundation Water Quality Index (NSFWQI)

NSFWQI can be calculated as follows (Abbasi 2012):

$$\text{NSFWQI} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i \times Q_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Where W_i : weight factor of the i^{th} parameter (Table A-1).

Q_i : sub-index quality value i^{th} parameter, can be obtained from the appropriate sub-index rating graph (Figures A-1).

Table (A-1): NSFWQI weight factors

Parameter	Weight factor
Dissolved oxygen (%sat)	0.17
Fecal coliform (#/100 mL)	0.16
pH (standard units)	0.11
Biochemical oxygen demand (mg/L)	0.11
Temperature change (degrees C)	0.10
Total phosphate (mg/L)	0.10
Nitrates (mg/L)	0.10
Turbidity (NTU)	0.08
Total suspended solids (mg/L)	0.07

Figure (A.a1): Q-value curves of NSFQI for parameters (temperature and phosphate), respectively (Water Research Center website).

Figure (A.b1): Q-value curves of NSFQI for parameters (nitrate and fecal coliform), respectively (Water Research Center website).

Figure (A.c1): Q-value curves of NSFQI for parameters (turbidity and pH), respectively (Water Research Center website).

Figure (A.d1): Q-value curves of NSFQI for parameters (BOD and DO), respectively (Water Research Center website).

NSFWQI is a reduction index, namely it is decreases with increasing water pollution. This index has a value between 0 to 100 and is classified according to (Table A-2). The rankings range from very bad to excellent based on the WQI scores (Brown et al. 1970).

Table (A-2): Water quality classification according to NSFWQI

Rank	NSFWQI Score
Excellent	91–100
Good	71–90
Medium	51–70
Bad	26–50
Very Bad	0–25

Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment Water Quality Index (CCMEWQI)

CCMEWQI can be calculated according to the following equation (CCME 2001):

$$CCMEWQI = 100 - \sqrt{\frac{F_1^2 + F_2^2 + F_3^2}{1.732}} \tag{A.2}$$

Where factors F_1 , F_2 , and F_3 are defined as scope, frequency and amplitude, respectively.

F_1 (Scope) represents the percentage of variables that do not meet their objectives at least once during the time period under consideration (failed variables), relative to the total number of measured variables:

$$F_1 = \left[\frac{\text{Number of failed variables}}{\text{Total number of variables}} \right] \times 100 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

F_2 (Frequency) represents the percentage of individual tests that do not meet objectives (failed tests):

$$F_2 = \left[\frac{\text{Number of failed tests}}{\text{Total number of tests}} \right] \times 100 \quad (\text{A.4})$$

F_3 (Amplitude) represents the amount by which failed test values do not meet their objectives. F_3 is calculated in three steps, as following:

1) The number of times by which an individual concentration is greater than (or less than, when the objective is a minimum) the objective is termed an “excursion” and is expressed as follows:

When the test value must not exceed the objective:

$$\text{excursion}_i = \left[\frac{\text{Failed test value}_i}{\text{Objective}_j} \right] - 1 \quad (\text{A.5-a})$$

For the cases in which the test value must not fall below the objective:

$$\text{excursion}_i = \left[\frac{\text{Objective}_j}{\text{Failed test value}_i} \right] - 1 \quad (\text{A.5-b})$$

2) The collective amount by which individual tests are out of compliance is calculated by summing the excursions of individual tests from their objectives and dividing by the total number of tests (both those meeting objectives and those not meeting objectives). This variable, referred to as the Normalized Sum of Excursions, or nse , which is calculated as:

$$nse = \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{Objective}_j}{\text{Total number of tests}} \right] \quad (\text{A.6})$$

3) F_3 is then calculated by an asymptotic function that scales the normalized sum of the excursions from objectives (nse) to yield a range between 0 and 100.

$$F_3 = \left[\frac{nse}{0.01nse + 0.01nse} \right] \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Therefore, five categories are suggested to categorize the water qualities which are summarized in Table A-3 (CCME 2001).

Table (A-3): CCMEWQI Categorization Schema

Ranks	CCMEWQI Score	Description
Excellent	95 – 100	Water quality is protected with a virtual absence of threat or impairment; conditions very close to natural or pristine levels.
Good	80 – 94	Water quality is protected with only a minor degree of threat or impairment; conditions rarely depart from natural or desirable levels.
Fair	65 – 79	Water quality is usually protected but occasionally threatened or impaired; conditions sometimes depart from natural or desirable levels.
Marginal	45 – 64	Water quality is frequently threatened or impaired; conditions often depart from natural or desirable levels.
Poor	0 – 44	Water quality is almost always threatened or impaired; conditions usually depart from natural or desirable levels.

Appendix B: Cross sections of study area along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city using GIS.

Figure (B-1): The location of cross sections of study area along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city, based on the field survey, using GIS.

Figure (B-2): Cross sections No.1, No.2 and No.3 of the study area along the Rosetta Branch based on the field survey

Figure (B-3): Cross sections No.4, No.5 and No.6 of the study area along the Rosetta Branch based on the field survey

Figure (B-4): Cross sections No.7, No.8 and No.9 of the study area along the Rosetta Branch based on the field survey

Figure (B-5): Cross sections No.10, No.11 and No.12 of the study area along the Rosetta Branch based on the field survey

Figure (B-6): Cross sections No.13, No.14 and No.15 of the study area along the Rosetta Branch based on the field survey

Figure (B-7): Cross sections No.16, No.17 and No.18 of the study area along the Rosetta Branch based on the field survey

Figure (B-8): Cross sections No.19, No.20 and No.21 of the study area along the Rosetta Branch based on the field survey

Figure (B-9): Cross sections No.22, No.23 and No.24 of the study area along the Rosetta Branch based on the field survey

Appendix C: The results of water quality management scenarios

Scenario No.1: Diverting of the industrial effluents to the city sewer system

- Salinity

Figure (C-1): Salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.1 compared to the simulated reference case

-DO

Figure (C-2): DO profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.1 compared to the simulated reference case

-BOD

Figure (C-3): BOD profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.1 compared to the simulated reference case

-FC

Figure (C-4): FC profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenairo No.1 compared to the simulated reference case

Scenario No.2: A 50% Reduction of the salinity concentrations of the Tala Drain

-Salinity

Figure (C-5): Salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.2 compared to the simulated reference case

Scenario No.3: A 25% Reduction of the Tala Drain discharge

-Salinity

Figure (C-6): Salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.3 compared to the simulated reference case

-DO

Figure (C-7): DO profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.3 compared to the simulated reference case

-BOD

Figure (C-8): BOD profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the scenario No.3 compared to the simulated reference case

-FC

Figure (C-9): BOD profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.3 compared to the simulated reference case

Scenario No.4: Diverting of the Tala Drain discharge to the nearest main drain

-Salinity

Figure (C-10): Salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.4 compared to the simulated reference case

-DO

Figure (C-11): DO profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.4 compared to the simulated reference case

-BOD

Figure (C-12): BOD profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.4 compared to the simulated reference case

-FC

Figure (C-13): FC profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.4 compared to the simulated reference case

Scenario No.5: A 25% Increase in the Rosetta Branch discharge

-Salinity

Figure (C-14): Salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying the Scenario No.5 compared to the simulated reference case

-DO

Figure (C-15): DO profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.5 compared to the simulated reference case

-BOD

Figure (C-16): BOD profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.5 compared to the simulated reference case

-FC

Figure (C-17): FC profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.5 compared to the simulated reference case

Scenario No.6: A 25% Decrease in the Rosetta Branch discharge

-Salinity

Figure (C-18): Salinity profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying the Scenario No.6 compared to the simulated reference case

-DO

Figure (C-19): DO profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.6 compared to the simulated reference case

-BOD

Figure (C-20): BOD profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.6 compared to the simulated reference case

-FC

Figure (C-21): FC profile of the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during the autumn, winter and spring due to applying of the Scenario No.6 compared to the simulated reference case.

Table (4-1): Correlation matrix for the analyzed parameters along the Rosetta Branch at Kafr El-Zayat city during 2014-2015

Parameter	Water temperature	TDS	Turbidity	pH	DO	Salinity	EC	BOD	COD	NO ₂	NO ₃	PO ₄	SO ₄	Fe	Mn	Cl	FC	Total algae
Water temperature	1.00																	
TDS	-0.23	1.00																
Turbidity	0.54	-0.12	1.00															
pH	0.14	-0.15	0.31	1.00														
DO	-0.68	0.20	-0.22	0.50	1.00													
Salinity	-0.23	1.00	-0.10	-0.15	0.20	1.00												
EC	0.01	0.96	0.05	-0.13	0.10	0.96	1.00											
BOD	0.08	0.43	-0.28	-0.24	-0.16	0.42	0.47	1.00										
COD	0.03	-0.16	0.23	0.16	0.09	-0.14	-0.10	0.25	1.00									
NO ₂	0.06	0.76	0.01	-0.11	0.13	0.76	0.78	0.52	0.22	1.00								
NO ₃	0.21	0.73	0.10	-0.14	-0.16	0.74	0.78	0.40	-0.02	0.68	1.00							
PO ₄	-0.49	0.82	-0.54	-0.10	0.31	0.80	0.70	0.50	-0.28	0.55	0.47	1.00						
SO ₄	0.03	0.88	0.15	-0.18	0.04	0.89	0.91	0.19	-0.24	0.71	0.75	0.55	1.00					
Fe	0.31	-0.22	0.19	0.10	-0.11	-0.21	-0.10	0.21	0.04	0.01	-0.20	-0.13	-0.10	1.00				
Mn	-0.14	-0.13	-0.31	-0.12	-0.21	-0.15	-0.16	0.32	-0.04	0.13	-0.24	0.20	-0.22	0.42	1.00			
Cl	0.20	0.38	-0.08	0.13	0.15	0.38	0.46	0.54	0.40	0.53	0.53	0.30	0.27	-0.17	-0.05	1.00		
FC	0.50	0.29	0.27	-0.26	-0.50	0.30	0.46	0.18	-0.29	0.09	0.49	0.01	0.49	0.22	-0.16	0.05	1.00	
Total algae	-0.66	-0.18	-0.34	-0.17	0.34	-0.17	-0.29	-0.08	0.12	-0.35	-0.36	0.07	-0.34	-0.13	0.08	-0.07	-0.44	1.00

- Shaded cells indicate moderate and strong correlations.